

**STUDYING THE PRECISION GRIP PERFORMANCE IN
PARKINSON'S DISEASE PATIENTS BY EXPERIMENTS AND
MODELING.**

A THESIS

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THESIS CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the thesis titled **Studying the precision grip performance in Parkinson's disease patients by experiments and modeling.**, submitted by **Ankur Gupta**, to the Indian Institute of Technology, Madras, for the award of the degree of **Doctor of Philosophy**, is a bona fide record of the research work done by him under our supervision. The contents of this thesis, in full or in parts, have not been submitted to any other Institute or University for the award of any degree or diploma.

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ABSTRACT

KEYWORDS: precision grip, grip force, Parkinson's disease, decision making, friction changes.

Parkinson's Disease (PD), is a neurodegenerative disorder characterized by loss of dopaminergic cells in substantia nigra pars compacta (SNc) —a key module of a subcortical cerebral circuit known as the Basal Ganglia (BG). Precision Grip (PG) is a grip formed by one of the fingers and the opposable thumb (Napier, 1956). In PG, the fingers apply horizontal forces called the Grip Forces (GFs) on the object, preventing it from slipping when it is lifted. Studies on PG performance on PD patients show impairments in GF generation. PD studies show that the controls and PD patients not on dopamine medication generate nearly similar safety margin (SM) whereas a higher SM was generated under the medicated (ON) state (Ingvarsson *et al.*, 1997). SM is defined as the difference between the actual GF generated and the minimum GF necessary to hold an object without slipping. The increase in SM is perhaps due to the L-Dopa induced hyperkinesia (Ingvarsson *et al.*, 1997). Variance in SM was also considerably higher in PD patients not on medication compared to controls and medicated PD patients (Ingvarsson *et al.*, 1997). Another study (Fellows *et al.*, 1998), which only considered the PD patients on medication and controls, observed that medicated subjects show a higher SM than controls (Fellows *et al.*, 1998).

This thesis attempts to explain the precision grip performance of the controls and PD patients (both in medicated and non-medicated state) using computational modeling.

In a PG task, if the same object is used i.e. physical properties like weight, size and surface curvature remains constant; still the GF developed is dependent on the skin friction—that is unrelated to Parkinsonian pathology. Changes in GF generated by PD patients must be interpreted after factoring in skin friction.

Therefore, in the first part of this thesis, a computational model was built for an experimental precision grip-lift task which is used to demonstrate the effect of skin friction on precision grip performance (PGP). Two forms of friction variation were considered: 1) intrinsic friction (high and low), and 2) acutely altered friction (dry and wet). The PGF was found to be dependent on the intrinsic friction and the SGF was dependent on the acute changes on friction. A computational model was developed to reflect the changes in PGF and SGF. This model was also used to understand the role of training in PGP. Simulation results suggest that in case of an acute change in friction, a sufficient training of parameters with the dry parameters as initial values, produce low performance errors with significantly higher computation time. However, in case of partial training of the dry parameters, though the errors obtained are higher, computation time is significantly reduced. This shows that the under dry condition controller parameters may be trained over many encounters with different objects but under suddenly reduced friction the controller parameters for dry case may be used as an initial for controller training.

In the second part of the study, computational model (of the previous study) is slightly modified and integrated into a decision making framework to generate the GFs in

healthy and PD (both ON and OFF medicated) cases. The model uses Go/Explore/NoGo (GEN) algorithm of (Magdoom *et al.*, 2011; Sukumar *et al.*, 2012; Chakravarthy, 2013; Muralidharan *et al.*, 2014) to maximize utility. Simulation studies suggest that the problem of safety margin generation is a decision making problem and PD patients with insufficient dopamine levels or on medication show altered grip force selection due to altered decision making.

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ABBREVIATIONS

ANOVA	Analysis of variance
APE	Average percentage error
BA	Brodmann's area
BART	Balloon Analog Risk Task
BG	Basal ganglia
cm	centimeter
DA	Dopamine
DM	Decision making
DP	Direct pathway
GA	Genetic Algorithm
GEN	Go-Explore-NoGo
GEN	Go/Explore/NoGo
GF	Grip force
GPe	Globus pallidus externa
GPi	Globus pallidus interna
Hz	Hertz
IP	Indirect pathway
IPS	Intraparietal Sulcus
LF	Lift force
LTD	Long-term depression
m	meters
mm	millimeter
MSNs	Medium spiny neurons
N	Newton
PD	Parkinson's Disease
PD ON	Parkinson's Disease patients on medication
PDOFF	Parkinson's Disease patients with medication withdrawal for >12 hours
PG	Precision Grip
PGBT	Precision grip balloon task

PGF	Peak grip force
PGLT	The Precision grip-lift task
PGP	Precision grip performance
PID controller	Proportional, integral and derivative controller
PMd	Dorsal premotor areas
PMv	Ventral premotor areas
PZ	Penalizing zone
r	Reward
RBNN	Radial Basis Function Neural Network
RL	Reinforcement learning
RZ	Rewarding zone
s	State
SGF	Steady state grip force
S-I	Primary somato-sensory cortex
S-II	Secondary somato- sensory cortex
SL	Supervised learning
SM	Safety margin
SNe	Substantia nigra pars compacta
SNr	Substantia nigra pars reticula
S-R	Stimulus-response
STN	Subthalamic nucleus
t	Trial
TD	Temporal Difference
U	Utility
UL	Unsupervised learning
V	Value
VTA	Ventral tegmental area
ZZ	Zero rewarding zone
α	Risk sensitivity

NOTATION

A_E	Gain of Explore
A_G	Gain of Go
A_N	Gain of NoGo
CE	Cost function to evaluate the performance of lift
CE_{GEN}	Cost function for training GEN parameters
C_G	Cost function for the grip force controller
C_L	Cost function for training the lift force controller
dt	Step interval (0.001 s)
dX_{fin}/dt	Finger velocity (in ms^{-1})
dX_o/dt	Object velocity (in ms^{-1})
E_G	Input error for the grip force controller
E_L	Input error for the lift force controller
F_{crit}	Slip force (in N)
F_f	The frictional force acting at the finger-object interface (in N)
F_{fin}	Net force acting on finger (in N)
F_G	Grip force (in N)
$F_{G,PID}$	Grip force generated by the grip force PID controller (in N)
F_{Gref}	Target grip force
F_L	Lift force (in N)
$F_{L,PID}$	Lift force generated by the lift force PID controller (in N)
F_n	Force normal to the table at the object-table interface (in N)
F_{noslip}	Frictional force required for no slip (in N)
F_o	Net force acting on object (in N)
F_{slip}	Maximum frictional force that can be generated (in N)
g	Acceleration due to gravity ($9.8 ms^{-2}$)
h	Risk
$K_{D,G}$	Differential gain for grip force controller
$K_{D,L}$	Differential gain for lift force controller
kg	kilogram
$K_{I,G}$	Integral gain for grip force controller
$K_{I,L}$	Integral gain for lift force controller
$K_{P,G}$	Proportional gain for grip force controller
$K_{P,L}$	Proportional gain for lift force controller
$max(X_{O,M})$	Maximum height to which the object was lifted during simulated lift (in m)
M_{fin}	Finger mass (assumed to be $M_o/10$)
M_o	Mass of object
M_p	Maximum overshoot
PGF_E	Peak grip force in experiments (in N)
PGF_M	Peak grip force in model (in N)
PID_{KG}	Controller parameters for F_G controller
$PID_{KG,dry}$	Grip force controller PID Parameter for the dry case
$PID_{KG,wet}$	Grip force controller PID Parameter for the wet case

PID_{KL}	Controller parameters for F_L controller
SGF_E	Stable grip force in experiments (in N)
SGF_M	Stable grip force in model (in N)
T_p	Time required for the response curve to peak
V_{CE}	A reward-like quantity, the average of which is linked to value
w_h	Weights for risk function
w_V	Weight for determining value
X_{fin}	Finger position (in m)
\dot{X}_{fin}	Velocity of finger
\ddot{X}_{fin}	Acceleration of finger
\bar{X}_{fin}	Average position of the finger
X_o	Object position (in m)
\dot{X}_o	Velocity of object
\ddot{X}_o	Acceleration of object
\bar{X}_o	Average position of the object
$\bar{X}_{O,M}$	Average object position (in simulated lift) from time when the object first reaches X_{ref} to the end of the lift (in m)
X_{ref}	Reference position (in m)
ΔF_{Gref}	Change in reference grip force
δ_{Lim}	Clamped/reduced levels of dopamine in PD condition
δ_{Med}	Additional dopamine available due to L-dopa medicine intake
ζ	Damping factor
η_V	Learning rate
λ_G	Sensitivity of Go component
λ_N	Sensitivity of NoGo component
μ	Friction coefficient
μ_d	Friction coefficient in dry condition
μ_w	Friction coefficient in wet condition
ξ	Risk prediction error
ρ	Output of RBFNN
σ_E	Spread of the Explore component
σ_X	Measure of variation in the position
σ_X	Standard deviation in position from time when object reaches X_{ref}
$\tau_{E,G}$	Time constant for the dynamics of E_G
$\tau_{F,G}$	Time constant for the dynamics of F_G
$\tau_{F,L}$	Time constant for the dynamics of F_L
ψ	Random vector
ω_n	Natural frequency

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Precision Grip (PG) is a special mode of gripping that involves holding a small object between one of the fingers and the opposable thumb (Napier, 1956). Emergence of an opposable thumb in the old world monkeys and great apes (Almecija *et al.*, 2010) marks an important milestone in the evolution of the motor system. Animals endowed with this special digital gift acquired greater skill in tool use, a function that involved dexterous application of PG.

In addition to having an obvious significance as a component of human motor function, PG also has an interesting clinical significance. As a simple non-invasive motor function, PG can be used as a convenient clinical tool for assessment of motor function. Accordingly, impairment in PG performance has been observed in a variety of motor and non-motor conditions including attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (Pereira *et al.*, 2000), writer's cramp (Serrien *et al.*, 2000), lower median nerve damage (Dun *et al.*, 2007), cerebral palsy (Eliasson *et al.*, 2006), dystonia (Nowak *et al.*, 2005), Huntington Disease (Gordon *et al.*, 2000), sensory impairments (Monzée *et al.*, 2003; Witney *et al.*, 2004) and Parkinson's Disease (Ingvarsson *et al.*, 1997; Fellows *et al.*, 1998).

Parkinson's Disease (PD), initially described as shaking palsy (Parkinson, 2002), is a neurodegenerative disorder characterized by loss of dopaminergic cells in substantia nigra pars compacta (SNc) a key module of a subcortical cerebral circuit known as the basal ganglia (BG). PD affects almost 1% of the population worldwide over the age of 60 years (Nussbaum *et al.*, 2003; de Lau *et al.*, 2006). The incidence of PD rises from 17.4 (50-59 years) to 93.1 (70-79 years) per 100 000 humans (Lees *et al.*, 2009). It was estimated that almost 7 million humans (70 per 100 000) suffer from PD in India (Behari *et al.*, 2002).

PD significantly impairs the patient's daily life (Magerkurth *et al.*, 2005), affecting motor (Marsden, 1982; Alexander *et al.*, 1989), cognitive (Marsden, 1982), affective (Hamakawa *et al.*, 1998) and autonomous domains (Magalhaes *et al.*, 1995; Kandel *et al.*, 2000a; Benedetti *et al.*, 2004). The four cardinal signs of PD are tremor (Conn, 2008; Jankovic, 2008), bradykinesia (Samii *et al.*, 2004; Jankovic, 2008; Rodriguez-Oroz *et al.*, 2009), rigidity (Samii *et al.*, 2004; Jankovic, 2008) and postural instability (Samii *et al.*, 2004; Jankovic, 2008; Yao *et al.*, 2013). However, PD is not exclusively a motor disorder, as it was thought earlier. Motor impairments in PD are seen in diverse motor modalities including reaching (Jaeger *et al.*, 1993; Helie *et al.*, 2013), eye movements (Alexander *et al.*, 1989; Hikosaka *et al.*, 2000; Helie *et al.*, 2013), handwriting (Phillips *et al.*, 1991; Gangadhar *et al.*, 2009; Helie *et al.*, 2013), speech (Speedie *et al.*, 1993), gait (Garcia-Rill, 1986; Hausdorff *et al.*, 1998; Helie *et al.*, 2013), posture (Mink, 1996; Plotnik *et al.*, 2011; Helie *et al.*, 2013) and precision grip (Ingvarsson *et al.*, 1997; Fellows *et al.*, 1998; Fellows *et al.*, 2004) etc. Similarly,

cognitive impairments are seen in various tasks like Wisconsin card sorting test (Owen *et al.*, 1992; Dubois *et al.*, 1996), tower of London test (Owen *et al.*, 1992; Dubois *et al.*, 1996), set shifting task (Owen *et al.*, 1992; Dubois *et al.*, 1996), spatial working memory task (Owen *et al.*, 1992), Mini-Mental State Exam (Riedel *et al.*, 2008) and Parkinson neuro-psychometric dementia assessment (Dubois *et al.*, 1996; Riedel *et al.*, 2008).

Over the last two or three decades computational models have emerged as powerful tools for understanding brain functions in normal as well as pathological conditions. Computational models have helped unravel the diverse and “mysterious” (Marsden, 1982) functions of BG and their impairments in PD patients. Computational models of BG function and their impairment under Parkinsonian conditions have been proposed in several motor domains including reaching (Magdoom *et al.*, 2011), eye movements (Krishnan *et al.*, 2011), handwriting (Gangadhar *et al.*, 2008; Gangadhar *et al.*, 2009), speech (Maya *et al.*, 2012) and gait (Muralidharan *et al.*, 2014). However, no computational model of PG in Parkinsonian condition exists as on date.

The key objective of this thesis is to construct a computational model of BG specifically to account for changes in PG performance in PD patients. An important class of computational models of BG is based on reinforcement learning (RL) framework, a branch of learning inspired by instrumental conditioning (Sutton *et al.*, 1998; O'Doherty *et al.*, 2004; Balleine *et al.*, 2009). A specific, RL-based approach to BG modeling, known as the Go-Explore-NoGo (GEN) approach was able to explain a

wide range of BG functions (Chakravarthy *et al.*, 2010; Krishnan *et al.*, 2011; Magdoom *et al.*, 2011; Kalva *et al.*, 2012; Sukumar *et al.*, 2012). The GEN approach in a modified form is used in the present thesis to model PG performance in normal and PD conditions.

Differences in PG performance between healthy controls and PD patients can be characterized in terms of mean and variance of grip force (Ingvarsson *et al.*, 1997; Fellows *et al.*, 1998). However, it must be noted that comparisons of grip forces developed in PD involves a factor—the skin friction—that is unrelated to Parkinsonian pathology. Changes in grip forces generated must be interpreted after factoring in skin friction. Grip forces generated are higher (lower) for conditions of lower (higher) skin friction, irrespective of changes in the central nervous system. The role of skin friction or the friction associated with the hand-object interface can be handled in two ways:

- By artificially normalizing the friction of hand-object interface by inserting a medium with a known friction value.
- By studying the effect of skin friction on PG performance.

Note that it is much harder to interpret changes in grip force generation in terms of the brain pathology, when the friction at the hand-object interface is not controlled and allowed to vary. In our model of PG performance in PD patients (Chapter 6) we assume constant friction and avoid the complications of a skin friction that varies

from individual to individual. However, we do take up the problem of the effect of skin friction in grip force generation in normal conditions in Chapter 5.

Reported studies show that PD patients generate an altered GF compared to controls. The reasons for this altered GF under medication and on withdrawal from medication are not clear. This thesis attempts to answer the question why PD patients generate an altered grip force using computational modeling. Furthermore, this is the first model for precision grip task for PD patients.

1.1 OBJECTIVES

Therefore, the objectives of the present thesis are as follows.

- To develop a computational model of precision grip-lift task for healthy controls.
- To obtain precision grip-lift task experimental data for healthy controls under variable friction conditions.
- To develop a risk based decision making in reinforcement learning framework model for precision grip task.
- To explain the grip force changes in Parkinson's disease patients using the experimental data (obtained from Ingvarsson *et al.* (1997) and Fellows *et al.* (1998))

1.2 OUTLINE OF THE THESIS

The thesis is outlined as follows.

In chapter 2, precision grip-lift task along with the grip force generation and control mechanism is described. A precision grip–lift task requires holding the object in a PG, composed by index finger and thumb (Napier, 1956), and lifting it to the desired height. The fingers generate grip force (GF) and lift force (LF). GF couples the fingers to the object and LF lifts the fingers. An insufficient GF poorly couples the object and finger; hence when LF is developed the fingers merely slide over the object and the object fails to lift. On the contrary, usage of a high GF might damage object and cause muscle fatigue. Therefore it is crucial to generate optimal GF. Various physical properties of the object and the finger-object interface (weight (Johansson *et al.*, 1988a; Forssberg *et al.*, 1992), size (Gordon *et al.*, 1991; Gordon *et al.*, 1992), surface curvature (Jenmalm *et al.*, 1998) and friction (Johansson *et al.*, 1984; Westling *et al.*, 1984b; Forssberg *et al.*, 1995; Saels *et al.*, 1999)) govern the GF developed. For controlling the force generation, sensory information about the object and limb position is obtained and transmitted via the spinal cord to the brain. In brain, various cortical and subcortical substrates receive this information. Primary somatic sensory cortex (S1) is one of the recipients of the information. S1 projects to secondary somatic sensory cortex and posterior parietal cortex. Posterior parietal cortex, which serves as the association area for integrating sensory and visual information, projects to primary motor cortex and premotor area. Primary motor cortex generates motor commands for force production. A copy of this motor

command is received by the basal ganglia which modulate the force by sending modulatory signals to the motor cortex.

In chapter 3, various aspects of motor plan execution together with models of precision grip task and basal ganglia are presented. The motor plan execution begins with the motor planning. Planning is important to minimize jerk (Hogan *et al.*, 1987), to reduce time of movement or improve accuracy (Meyer *et al.*, 1988). This is followed by actual movement execution in feedforward mode or feedback mode or a combination of feedforward and feedback modes. Once the movement goal is successfully achieved, the performed action must be updated so as to improve the future performance. Here motor learning sets in. Motor learning can be done in three different ways: the supervised learning, the unsupervised learning and the reinforcement learning. After presenting how the various stages of motor function (planning, execution and learning) are important in motor tasks, the PG models are introduced followed by the models of BG involved in motor control and learning.

Chapter 4 presents a computational model for a precision grip-lift task which is used to demonstrate the effect of skin friction on precision grip performance (PGP) in chapter 5. In this study, PGP is characterized by two metrics: peak grip force (PGF) and steady state grip force (SGF) generated. Thereafter in chapter 6, a small modification of this model is used to illustrate the role of risk based decision making in reinforcement learning framework on variability in GF generation in controls and PD patients. In computational model of Chapter 4, fingers apply GF and LF on an

object. The fingers and object interact at the finger-object interface via friction. This model comprises of two proportional-integral-derivative (PID) controllers—one for GF and one for LF. The PID controller parameters are trained using genetic algorithm.

Considering all the physical parameters of the object (weight, size and surface curvature) remain constant except friction, the GF developed must depend only on the friction coefficient and the motor control commands. The variation in GF development due to friction changes is described in chapter 5. This is followed by a chapter on how controls and PD patients differ in the GF generation mechanism.

Chapter 5 contains an experimental study and a computational model showing the role of skin friction on variation of GF. Specifically, it studies the effect of two types of variation in friction—acute and intrinsic. Acute change in friction refers to the friction of the skin in its natural dry condition, and the reduced friction under wet conditions. Intrinsic differences in friction are considered by considering people with intrinsically high and low skin friction values. In the experimental part of the study, subjects were asked to precision grip-lift the object under two conditions—intrinsic dry condition (when the fingers were not artificially wetted) and wet condition (when the fingers were saturated with water). The subjects were classified into high friction and low friction subjects based on the friction coefficient between the fingers and the object in dry condition. The two groups were separately analyzed. Further addition to this study was the computational model to match the human performance in dry and wet

conditions. The model used for this task is described in chapter 4. The simulation results obtained for dry condition were very close ($< 1\%$ error) to the experimentally obtained human PGP. One of the key aspects of this study was to understand the ease with which the model derived under dry conditions can be adapted to the wet condition by partial retraining of the model. To understand the same, dry condition parameters were used as initial values for training the parameters for the wet condition. Changing the friction to wet condition value without training the dry parameters, the PGF error obtained was $38.49\% \pm 50.07\%$ and SGF error was $18.90\% \pm 36.97\%$. However, when the parameters were fully trained results show $<1\%$ error when compared to the experimental results. With partial training (5 iterations compared to >50 for full training) the model showed PGF errors as $2.3\% \pm 1.33\%$ and SGF errors as $3.40\% \pm 1.50\%$. Therefore, the GF generation under reduced friction coefficient can be achieved by the use of parameters for intrinsic friction and a small amount of retraining.

In chapter 6, computational model (presented in chapter 4) is slightly modified and integrated into a decision making framework to generate the grip forces in healthy and PD (both on and off medicated cases). The PID controller for generating the grip force is replaced by a second order controller. A Radial Basis Function Neural Network (RBFNN) was created which associated the value and risk to each target grip force (F_{Gref}). Now the F_{Gref} must be chosen such that the utility is maximized. Value and risk together were used to determine the utility of the given F_{Gref} . For determining the maximum of the utility a Go/Explore/NoGo (GEN) equation was used. The

contribution of the three GEN components was modulated by dopamine. Since dopamine producing cells are decreased in PD, the model was simulated with reduced DA to simulate PD condition. Further, the PD ON condition was simulated by adding additional dopamine due to medication. The model was used to simulate the results of two experimental results presented by Ingvarsson *et al.* (1997) (both sandpaper and silk surfaces) and Fellows *et al.* (1998). In this study, we attempt to understand the changes in GF patterns in healthy controls, PD patients on medication (PD ON) and PD patient with the medication withdrawal for >12 hours (PDOFF) using experimental studies and modeling.

Chapter 7 contains a discussion of the thesis.

CHAPTER 2

PRECISION GRIP

Every day we interact with numerous objects like door handles, coffee cups, pens, needles, spoons, hammers etc. to accomplish certain tasks. These interactions can be divided into two main groups: non-prehensile and prehensile. The movements in which the object is not secured by being wrapped around are known as non-prehensile movements, whereas manipulations involving grasping the object are known as prehensile movements (Napier, 1956). A further classification of prehensile movements can be power grip and PG (Napier, 1956) (Fig. 2.1). Power grip is formed when the fingers envelope the object completely with the palm coming into contact with the object e.g. holding railing or hammer. As the name indicates, power grip can generate high forces but may not be suitable for tasks requiring finer force control. PG, however, requires the object to be grasped between the tips of the thumb and a finger (mostly index finger) and gives its user the ability to finely control the gripping forces.

2.1 PRECISION GRIP

PG is a type of grip formed by the thumb in opposition to any finger to hold a small object in the grip (Napier, 1956). An opposable thumb to other fingers is unique to old world monkeys and great apes (Jones *et al.*, 2006). The *homo sapiens*' success can be attributed to tool making (Marzke, 1997; Susman, 1998) and dexterous manipulations

of these tools in PG (Moyà-Solà *et al.*, 1999; Ambrose, 2001; Young, 2003; Jones *et al.*, 2006). Thanks to their comparatively larger thumbs than those of non-human primates, humans are able to form a more stable PG.

Fig. 2.1: Example of power grip (left) and precision grip (right).

The dexterity with which objects can be manipulated by PG has opened a new field of study of motor system — one that involves study of the development and control of the PG. This simple, non-invasive motor performance tool enables clinical researchers to assess motor integration by studying the loss of functionality (Müller *et al.*, 1994a) in PG task. Accordingly motor function in a variety of motor disorders including for example: attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (Pereira *et al.*, 2000), writer's cramp (Serrien *et al.*, 2000), lower median nerve damage (Dun *et al.*, 2007), cerebral palsy (Eliasson *et al.*, 2006), dystonia (Nowak *et al.*, 2005), Huntington Disease (Gordon *et al.*, 2000), sensory impairments (Witney *et al.*, 2004) and PD (Ingvarsson *et al.*, 1997; Fellows *et al.*, 1998) could be assessed through various modifications of the PG-lift task

2.2 THE PRECISION GRIP-LIFT TASK (PGLT)

The PGLT is an experimental setup which requires gripping an object containing force sensors (to measure the compressive strength) in the pinch grip formed by the thumb and index finger. The aim of the task is to reach the object, grip it in PG and then lift it to the marked/target height.

Fig. 2.2: Forces acting on the object.

PGLT requires generation of two forces (Fig. 2.2): GF and LF. GF couples the fingers to the object so that the object can be secured in the grip while LF generates the required force for lifting the object up. Successful PGLT requires a delicate control of these two forces.

Sufficient LF is required to overcome the objects weight and to lift the object off the table on which it rests. A low LF would not be able to lift the object and a very high LF would generate high object velocities thus making the object overshoot the

required position. However, LF alone is insufficient to lift the object as it is coupled to the object through GF via a finger-object friction interface.

Adequate GF is very important for PG because insufficient GF will prevent the object from being lifted (if the object rests on the table) but if the object was already lifted, a reduction in GF may result in slip. Hence, for a given task it may seem appropriate to generate very high GF. This scenario might be equally disastrous as the previous case. Generating high amounts of force will require continuous muscle contraction which can lead to loss of performance (reduced peak tension or force, shortening velocity, power output, prolonged twitch duration etc.) and fatigue (Edwards, 1981; Fitts, 1996). Hence generation of optimal GF is very important (for an example refer to Box 1).

BOX 1: An example showing the importance of optimal grip force.

To illustrate the importance of optimal grip force, and the fine motor control that we exercise at our fingertips across several joints, let us take a simple task of transporting an egg from a tray to a plate using two fingers (index finger and thumb) PG. Here we discuss the four scenarios (a) when the GF is not sufficiently large (b) initially optimal GF is generated which is reduced to insufficient levels during the transportation (c) when very high GFs are generated on the egg and (d) optimal GF is generated on the object. Case (a) will prevent the egg to be properly gripped and hence transporting the

egg in PG is impossible; Case (b) will cause the egg to be initially lifted but once GF reduces, the egg slips from the grip hence the task will end up in failure; Case (c) will crush the egg so the task never reaches completion; and Case (d) will generate sufficient GF to make transporting of the egg possible without breakage and slip. Hence, it is very critical that the GF generated is optimal and not inadequate (which might prevent the task to end in failure) or excess (which might damage the object being gripped and can cause fatigue to the user) (Gordon *et al.*, 1993).

Post-training constant weight trial, GF profile shows a gradual increase in GF to reach a peak and its return to a steady state value (Fig. 2.3 (a, b)). Various components of the GF profile are as follows: PGF which is the maximum GF generated; SGF which refers to the steady state value of GF; slip force (F_{crit}) which is the minimum amount of GF required to prevent the object from slipping; and safety margin (SM) which is the difference between SGF and F_{crit} . PGF is crucial in the initial lifting process without slip. Once the task is learnt, variations in SGF are reduced and also the subjects generate lower SGFs, with smaller safety margins. For a particular subject for the same amount of LF and friction conditions the F_{crit} obtained tends to be nearly constant (Westling *et al.*, 1984b). Hence, it is expected that the SM, where $SM = SGF - F_{crit}$, would also be constant. Interestingly this is not the case (refer Fig. 2.3 (a)). The variation of the SM is due to the signal dependent noise in muscle activation, the higher the muscle activation the more is the noise (Harris *et al.*, 1998; Lee *et al.*,

1998; Hamilton *et al.*, 2004). The focus of this thesis is to understand the SM generation, its variability and its variation in PD patients.

Fig. 2.3: PG force profiles for lifting task. (a) Single subject grip force profiles for 169gm object weight; (b) shows a typical GF profile with various component markings.

Johansson *et al.* (1988b) demonstrated the SM in controls to be 40-50% of slip force (Johansson *et al.*, 1988b). A high SM is employed to prevent the object from slipping due to internal (changes in acceleration due to arm motion) which may be a result of internal perturbations (Flanagan *et al.*, 1990; Flanagan *et al.*, 1993; Flanagan *et al.*, 1994; Werremeyer *et al.*, 1997) and/or external perturbations (random changes in object load) (Eliasson *et al.*, 1995)— motor activity is optimized for internal perturbations and this optimality is lost on the addition of an external perturbation (Charlesworth *et al.*, 2011; Sober *et al.*, 2012; Wolpert *et al.*, 2012). An excessive SM is undesirable as it would cause muscle fatigue and may even lead to crushing of the object.

When encountering the object for the first time the object's properties are unknown. The first step in PGLT is generating an internal representation of the object (Gordon *et al.*, 1994). In a visually guided task, information about weight (Johansson *et al.*, 1988a; Forssberg *et al.*, 1992), size (Gordon *et al.*, 1991; Gordon *et al.*, 1992), surface curvature (Jenmalm *et al.*, 1998) and friction (Johansson *et al.*, 1984; Westling *et al.*, 1984b; Forssberg *et al.*, 1995; Saels *et al.*, 1999) is used to select appropriate internal model. The muscles are activated based on the motor program. From the moment the fingers come into contact with the object, GF and LF begin to increase simultaneously (Forssberg *et al.*, 1991a; Johansson *et al.*, 1994). Yet, the object is not lifted from the table until the LF is more than the weight of the object. During the entire lifting process the LF is kept sufficiently higher than the object weight to prevent slip (Forssberg *et al.*, 1992). After a contact is established with the object and there is a mismatch between the anticipated output and the actual output, a mismatch signal is generated which is used to update the estimated physical properties and correct the sensory-motor program (Wolpert *et al.*, 1995; Wolpert *et al.*, 2001; Davidson *et al.*, 2003; Flanagan *et al.*, 2003; Nowak *et al.*, 2004; Schmitz *et al.*, 2005). A new set of motor commands based on the new internal representation of the object is created and executed (Johansson, 1999; Wolpert *et al.*, 2001). All the internal representations and motor commands are eventually translated into the forces (Fig. 2.4). Hence successful execution of PGLT depends crucially on the generation of two forces: LF and GF.

Fig. 2.4: Schematic illustrating the various components of FG generation (redrawn based on Schmitz *et al.* (2005)).

2.3 NEURAL CONTROL OF GRIP FORCE GENERATION

It will be of interest to discuss here how the SM is generated and by what neural circuitry. Before this we will look into the details of how the two primary forces (LF and GF) are generated in PGLT.

The sequence of neural processes leading to generation movement can be broken down into the following components: determining the physical properties of the object visually; transmission of these signals to various regions in the brain; determination of motor output; the transmission of motor signals to the spinal cord and then to the end effector—the muscle.

The initial conformation of a particular joint and the muscle is obtained via signal from the neuromuscular spindle (information about muscle length), Golgi tendon (information about muscle tension) and Ruffini and Pacinian corpuscles (information about joint configuration and changes in the configuration).

These signals are then transmitted to the spinal cord through their respective nerve fibers. Spinal cord contains a group of neurons called motor neurons which are involved in reflex actions (like withdrawal of hand after a pin prick). By having a short latency based reflex system, the disastrous effects of an adverse situation (pin prick in this case) due to long latency of supra spinal structures can be prevented.

The sensory information then travels to the subcortical structures mainly cerebellum and thalamus. Cerebellum is involved in motor learning (Fiez *et al.*, 1992; Thach, 1996), movement timing and planning (Ivry *et al.*, 1988; Müller *et al.*, 1994b); it also functions as a storage area for internal/ forward models (Kawato *et al.*, 2003). In PGLT it is observed that damage to dentate nucleus, a part of cerebellum, or its afferent input (cerebellar atrophy) results in loss of temporal coordination between the proximal muscles (lifting the object) and the fingers (gripping the object) and causes generation of abnormally high GF values (Fellows *et al.*, 2001). However, such patients do not show slow rate of grip force development. Hence, the cerebellum is involved in temporal coordination of multi-joint movement sequences and a damage to dentate nucleus or afferent input effect the sensorimotor processing which eventually leads to mistiming of GF generation (Fellows *et al.*, 2001).

Another key site of sensory input is the thalamus. On one hand thalamus receives the sensory input from the spinal cord and relays it to the somatic-sensory cortex and on the other it receives the information from basal ganglia and sends it to spinal cord. A dedicated region in thalamus projects to the primary somato-sensory cortex (S-I) (Strick, 1976). S-I is located in postcentral gyrus and contains four key areas Brodmann's area (BA) 1, 2, 3a and 3b. BA 3a and 3b is the site for majority of thalamic fiber termination. In turn the BA 3a and 3b project to BA 1 and BA 2. There is a high interconnectivity observed among these four areas. Each of these four areas project to the secondary somato-sensory cortex (S-II), which via the insular cortex innervate the temporal lobe for tactile memory formation. S-I also projects to the posterior parietal cortex (BA 5 and 7). These areas serve as association areas where mechanoreceptor information, proprioceptive information and visual information is integrated (Kandel *et al.*, 2000b).

Primary motor cortex (involved in control the movement execution) and premotor areas (involved in motor preparation through sensory and motor planning) receive inputs from BA 5 and BA 7 (Kandel *et al.*, 2000b). Ventral premotor area also receives inputs from area 46 which is involved in working memory. Davare *et al.* (2006) showed the specific role played by the dorsal and ventral premotor areas (PMd and PMv respectively) in PG task. The authors concluded that transient virtual lesions in either left or right PMv impairs correct finger position on the object; sequential recruitment of hand is impaired by contralateral PMv lesion and left PMd lesions affect the grasping and lifting phases (Davare *et al.*, 2006). Hence, the dorsal and

ventral premotor areas control different phases of the PG in humans (Davare *et al.*, 2006). The premotor areas receive inputs from cerebellum and basal ganglia (a separate section deals with the role of basal ganglia in PG). The final PG output is a result of direct spinal projections (via cortico-spinal) from the primary motor cortex (Muir *et al.*, 1983; Lemon *et al.*, 1995).

2.3.1 Basal ganglia in PG

The BG system consists of seven nuclei (refer Fig. 2.5) : caudate nucleus, putamen, globus pallidus interna (GPi) and globus pallidus externa (GPe), subthalamic nucleus (STN), substantia nigra pars compacta (SNc) and substantia nigra pars reticula (SNr). Caudate and putamen together form the striatum. The GPe, STN, GPi are arranged in two parallel paths viz. direct pathway (DP) and indirect pathway (IP). The direct pathway consists of inhibitory projections from the striatum to GPi. The indirect pathway has inhibitory projections from the striatum to GPe which in turn inhibit STN; the excitatory back projections from the STN project to GPe. STN also projects to GPi via excitatory connections. Now the DP and IP contain 1 and 2 inhibitory connections, respectively. Presence of another inhibitory connection between the GPi and thalamus makes the net output of DP excitatory and the net output of IP inhibitory. Thalamus projects back to the cortex thereby closing the cortical-BG-thalamo-cortical loop. SNc projects the dopaminergic projections to the STR (Mink, 1996; Smith *et al.*, 1998). Interestingly, the dopamine (DA) levels in striatum enable switching between DP and IP. The DP is selected for higher levels of DA and the IP for low levels of DA (Sutton *et al.*, 1998; Frank, 2005; Wu *et al.*,

2009). The DP is known to facilitate movement and hence called as Go pathway whereas the IP inhibits movement and thus is referred as NoGo pathway. Therefore switching between the Go and NoGo pathway is brought about by striatal dopamine levels (Albin *et al.*, 1989; Sutton *et al.*, 1998; Frank, 2005; Wu *et al.*, 2009). This Go and NoGo framework seems to be valid for binary action selection tasks but in case of more than two choices the selection using Go/NoGo might be difficult to explain. To address this question Chakravarthy *et al.* (2010) proposed presence of an Explore regime between the Go and NoGo regimes and emergence of the explore regime for intermediate levels of dopamine. So now the overall description of functional regimes of BG changes from Go-NoGo to Go-Explore-NoGo.

Fig. 2.5: The Basal Ganglia network with DP (Direct Pathway) and IP (Indirect Pathway) specified.

In a PG task, different aspects of motor tasks are controlled by different areas of basal ganglia (for a summary refer to Fig. 2.6). The two broad aspects of PG are planning and modulation of GF. Both these aspects are dealt by basal ganglia. A task requiring a constant or a variable GF amplitude production activated caudate, putamen, GPe, GPi and STN (Vaillancourt *et al.*, 2007) but selection was limited to the anterior BG i.e. caudate, anterior putamen and GPe. In another study, Pope *et al.* (2005) (which involved four tasks that required a switching between two force amplitude levels and relative timing) also showed that anterior basal ganglia was highly active for tasks requiring switching between two force amplitude levels but not for the task with varied timing and constant force amplitude. Hence these areas are involved in initial selection of GF.

Another aspect of planning of movement is memory. In the absence of previous experience with the object the uncertainty in estimation of object properties is high. Memory plays a crucial role in minimizing the uncertainty involved while the interacting with the same or identical object. Initial GF generation is entirely feed-forward process which is shaped by the previous experience (Johansson *et al.*, 1992b; Gordon *et al.*, 1993). Wasson *et al.* (2007) demonstrated that the activation of putamen and caudate increase with an increase in predictability of the GF. Boecker *et al.* (2005) also demonstrated the role of anterior BG in planning aspects of in a task involving predictability in lifting the object.

After the initial selection of the parameters, a different set of parameters is required in to be regulated for lifting the object successfully in PG. These are the rate at which GF and LF develops and, amplitude of the GF generated. In a visually guided PG task, it was shown that STN and GPi scaled with the rate of change of force production whereas GPe and putamen activity increased with the duration (Vaillancourt *et al.*, 2004; Prodoehl *et al.*, 2008). fMRI studies reveal contralateral and ipsilateral fronto-parietal areas and sub-cortical motor structures concurrently working in a PGLT (Ehrsson *et al.*, 2003).

Larger objects are lifted with higher peak GF (Gordon *et al.*, 1991). A Positron emission tomography (PET) study shows that contralateral posterior putamen and thalamus are activated when lifting objects with different weights. Interestingly, putamen was found to be active when lifting the heavy objects (Kinoshita *et al.*, 2000). Further investigation of the basal ganglia nuclei involved in GF amplitude production identified GPi and STN involvement with amplitude scaling whereas GPe, putamen and caudate did not show an increase in activation levels (Spraker *et al.*, 2007).

	<u>Planning</u>		<u>Parameterization</u>	
	Prediction	Selection	Amplitude	Rate
Caudate	✓	✓		
A. Putamen	✓	✓		
GPe		✓		
P. Putamen			✓	
GPi			✓	✓
STN			✓	✓
	Boecker et al. 2005 Wasson et al. 2007	Pope et al. 2005 Vaillancourt et al. 2007	Kinoshita et al. 2000 Spraker et al. 2007	Vaillancourt et al. 2004 Prodoehl et al. 2008

Fig. 2.6: Involvement of various basal ganglia nucleus in controlling the various planning and modulation of GF. Redrawn from Prodoehl *et al.* (2009)

In summary, BG is involved in planning and modulation of GF. Anterior BG (caudate, anterior putamen, and GPe) plans the initial GF production whereas posterior BG (posterior putamen, GPi and STN) modulates the GF on a dynamic basis.

In PD, the striatal dopamine levels reduce due to loss of dopamine producing cells, which affects action selection function of basal ganglia. (Chakravarthy *et al.*, 2010; Kalva *et al.*, 2012). Since PG performance involves selection of appropriate grip force levels, loss of dopamine cells results in PG-related impairments also. It is seen that the controls and PD OFF patients generate nearly similar SGFs (Ingvarsson *et al.*, 1997), whereas a higher SGF was generated in ON medication conditions (Ingvarsson *et al.*, 1997). A higher variance in SGF was also observed in the PD OFF patients compared to PD ON patients (Ingvarsson *et al.*, 1997). The higher SM generated might be a

result of L-Dopa induced hyperkinesias (Ingvarsson *et al.*, 1997; Gordon *et al.*, 1999). Fellows *et al.* (1998) also showed that the PD patients generate a higher SGF compared to controls but they failed to mention the PD OFF patients.

Our aim is to model this PG force behavior exhibited by the PD patients. In the following chapter we will discuss various models of PG performance.

CHAPTER 3

MODELS OF MOTOR CONTROL AND PRECISION GRIP

Models reflect our understanding of a real-world system. In computational neuroscience, particularly, models allow us to integrate information about a neurobiological system arriving from diverse sources including functional imaging, electrophysiology, anatomy, lesion and clinical studies and psychophysics. Models give an explicit form to the intuitive ideas and hypotheses regarding the function of a neural system. They also allow us to make predictions which may be tested by further experimentation. Considering the expense and intricacy involved in performing a wet lab experiment, models may also reduce the number of experiments that need to be performed in order to gain a comprehensive understanding of a neurobiological system.

Subsequent to the formal classification of power grip and precision grip by Napier (1956), a lot of research was directed towards understanding how humans grip objects. Yet robotic grippers developed till date are task specific (Stanger *et al.*, 1994; Schraft *et al.*, 2005; Brogårdh, 2007) and do not match the grace and dexterity of the human hand (Bicchi, 2000). This poses a serious question: ‘do we completely understand human gripping?’ In order to answer this question there is a need to review the existent literature on models of human gripping. But before the models of human gripping are described, we will first briefly discuss the various components of

general motor function viz., 1) motor planning, 2) motor control and 3) motor learning.

Consider a reaching task which requires moving a hand from point A to point B (Fig. 3.1A). There exists an infinite number of trajectories that connect A and B (Fig. 3.1A). Before the actual movement begins, the optimal trajectory to be taken (say, T_2 in the present example) must be planned and an appropriate motor command must be identified (Sober *et al.*, 2003; Sober *et al.*, 2005). Actual movement follows the planning stage. Here a continuous comparison of the realized trajectory and target trajectory is made, and in case of a mismatch the trajectory is corrected. The performance of the task is evaluated and internal parameters are updated to improve the performance in the next trial, a process that constitutes motor learning. Hence effective movement execution involves motor planning, motor control and motor learning (Miall *et al.*, 1996). We will now discuss each of these three aspects of motor function individually.

Fig. 3.1: An illustration of point to point movement from Point A to Point B. (A) the three possible trajectories between the two points are T_1 , T_2 and T_3 . (B) the possible trajectory (T_0) when obstacles (O) are encountered.

3.1 MOTOR PLANNING

What is the purpose of planning? Why do we need to plan the movement? Some studies (Rosenbaum *et al.*, 1995; Haggard, 1998; Rosenbaum *et al.*, 2001) suggest that the goal of planning might be to minimize jerk (Hogan *et al.*, 1987), to reduce time or improve accuracy (Meyer *et al.*, 1988). For example, in the above example of reaching task, adding obstacles changes the trajectory (Fig. 3.1B) taken in the absence of obstacles (Fig. 3.1A). Subjects select such trajectories to avoid collisions with the obstacles (Sabes *et al.*, 1997; Sabes, 2000). It is also demonstrated that task complexity (Haggard, 1998), arm dynamics (Sabes *et al.*, 1997), cost of movement (Zhang *et al.*, 2010), object orientation (Sabes *et al.*, 1997), and possible collisions with obstacles on the path (Sabes *et al.*, 1997; Sabes, 2000) also play a crucial role in planning. In a precision grip lifting task, subjects employ different rates of GF increase when lifting objects of different weights prior to lift-off (Johansson, 1998). This prior knowledge about the target GF that is displayed, even before the hand comes into contact with the object, suggests that the GF generation is planned before the movement is executed (Johansson, 1998). Furthermore, the same authors also showed that object properties (like friction and shape) determine the initial forces required for grip-lift task. However, in the absence of visual feedback information about the object's physical properties is not available until a contact is made with the object. It takes a delay of over 100 ms for the sensorimotor control system to use the updated objects parameters (Gordon *et al.*, 1993; Johansson, 1998). In the absence of the knowledge about the objects properties, the initial motor plan used is the one used for the previous lift (Johansson, 1998). This further supports the notion that the visual

cues influence the initial grip force (Johansson, 1998; Monzée *et al.*, 2003) and planning precedes the movement execution.

Fig. 3.2: Models of motor control (A) Feedforward control (Adapted from Kawato *et al.* (1998)), (B) Feedback control (Adapted from Kawato *et al.* (1998)), (C) Hybrid control (Modified from Wolpert *et al.* (2000)).

3.2 MOTOR CONTROL

Once the movement is planned, the next step is to execute the movement. This can be done in three modes: the feedforward control mode (Fig. 3.2A), feedback control mode (Fig. 3.2B) and a hybrid (Fig. 3.2C) of the two (Desmurget *et al.*, 2000; Seidler *et al.*, 2004). In feedforward control, the desired state information serves as the input based on which the internal model generates a feedforward motor command that updates the state (Johansson, 1998; Desmurget *et al.*, 2000; Seidler *et al.*, 2004). In such a control schema, the model does not receive any information about the performance and solely relies on the internal model for its performance. Due to the inherent nature of the feedforward control, the control signal generated cannot be modified after it is sent. In contrast, the feedback control requires difference between the desired state and the current state, the difference is the performance error, as the input (Kawato, 1999). Based on the input and controller (such as Proportional, integral and derivative feedback controller), a feedback motor command is generated which in turn updates the state (Kawato, 1999). This control mechanism typically has large latencies (Johansson *et al.*, 1992a; Kawato, 1999) but has improved performance in terms of error detection and correction when compared to feedforward control (Desmurget *et al.*, 2000; Seidler *et al.*, 2004). In summary, the former control strategy has poor accuracy and the latter control strategy has large delays. These limitations of the individual control systems can be overcome by using a hybrid control system that aims at combining the advantages of both the feedforward and feedback control (Desmurget *et al.*, 2000).

A variety of models for feedforward, feedback and hybrid controls have been proposed (Kawato *et al.*, 1987; Kawato *et al.*, 1992; Kawato, 1999; Sabes, 2000; Wolpert *et al.*, 2000; Kawato *et al.*, 2003). In a trajectory tracking task, if a feedforward control is employed then based on the desired trajectory a suitable inverse model is chosen which generates the feedforward motor command. The motor command then activates the muscles which change the position of the arm. The use of a well-trained inverse model would cause the actual trajectory and the desired trajectory to be identical (Fig. 3.2A). When a feedback controller is employed, the trajectory error (difference between the desired trajectory and the realized trajectory) serves as the input to the controller. The controller generates feedback motor command which in turn corrects the object trajectory. In a hybrid model (Fig. 3.2C) a combination of both the feedforward and feedback control is used. The desired trajectory and estimated trajectory are compared to determine the trajectory error which is input to the feedback controller that generates feedback motor command. The feedback motor command along with the feedforward motor command is sent to the hand to execute the movement. Sensory feedback is used to evaluate the performance of the motor task (Kawato *et al.*, 1987; Kawato *et al.*, 1992; Sabes, 2000; Wolpert *et al.*, 2000).

Another critical element of motor control machinery is the internal model. An internal model is a process by which the motor outcome of the motor command is estimated (forward model) or a motor command is generated to obtain a particular motor outcome (inverse model) (Flanagan *et al.*, 1997). However, Miall *et al.* (1996) added

cognitive model to this list. Internal models were then defined to be of three types: forward model, cognitive model and inverse model (Miall *et al.*, 1996).

- The forward model receives current state and efference copy of the motor command to predict the next state (Miall *et al.*, 1996). In other words, it emulates the normal response of the motor system to motor command. For example, during an arm movement, information about the joint angles and velocities forms the current state. Current state serves as the input to the forward model. Based on the past knowledge of the inputs and the system dynamics, the forward model generates the motor command for new states (Miall *et al.*, 1996). Interestingly, the forward model has one-to-one or many-to-one mappings, further supporting the theory that redundant hand configurations can result in the same endpoint.
- The cognitive model receives the information about the previous states of the environment and predicts the future behavior of the environment (Miall *et al.*, 1996). Whereas forward models emulate the behavior of the motor system, cognitive models emulate the behavior of the environment. For example, when we try to catch a ball we are using our knowledge of normal behavior of the physical world. Any deviation in the expected trajectory of the ball is likely to produce a sense of disbelief (Spelke *et al.*, 1994), which is caused by the operation of a cognitive model of the environment.
- The inverse model is basically an “inverse” of the forward model. It estimates the motor command that is likely to produce an observed state of the motor system viz., positions and velocities (Miall *et al.*, 1996). One problem with the inverse model is its possible non-uniqueness. Since a forward model often involves a many-to-one mapping, a unique inverse model may not exist.

3.3 MOTOR LEARNING

Three learning mechanisms are thought to underlie human motor learning: 1) supervised learning, 2) unsupervised learning and 3) reinforcement learning.

Fig. 3.3: Figure showing the schema of (A) Supervised learning, (B) Unsupervised learning, (C) Reinforcement learning. (Adapted from (Doya, 2000))

3.3.1 Supervised learning (SL)

Supervised learning (Fig. 3.3A) requires mapping the input data $[x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n]$ to the target/desired output data $[y_{d1}, y_{d2}, y_{d3}, \dots, y_{dn}]$ by minimizing the difference between the predicted output $[y_1, y_2, y_3, \dots, y_n]$ and the target output. If we consider a simple linear model, the predicted output is given as

$$y_i = \sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij} x_j \quad (3.1)$$

where, w_{ij} is the weight between the j^{th} input and i^{th} output. The aim is to minimize the cost function,

$$E = \sum_{i=1}^n ||y_{di} - y_i ||^2 \quad (3.2)$$

by updating the weights as

$$\Delta w_{ij} = \eta \delta_i x_j \quad (3.3)$$

where, η is the learning rate and $\delta_i = (y_{di} - y_i)$

In the motor system, the cerebellum is thought to be a site for supervised learning (Marr, 1969; Ito, 1989; Doya, 2000). The climbing fibers from the Inferior Olive with a “special one-to-one relationship with the cerebellar Purkinje cell” (Marr, 1969) cause long-term depression (LTD) of the Purkinje cell synapses (Doya, 2000). Purkinje cells also receive excitatory connections from the axons of the granule cells (Ito, 1989). If the inputs from the climbing fibers and the axons of granule cells arrive within a short time duration, LTD is produced (Ito, 1989; Ito, 2000). However if only one of the fibers is stimulated, the LTD is not induced (Ito, 1989; Ito, 2000). In supervised learning, a teaching signal, and therefore an error signal, is required. This error signal (in cerebellum) is thought to be carried by the climbing fibers from the Inferior Olive (Doya, 1999; Doya, 2000; Ito, 2000) (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3.4: The supervised learning model of cerebellum. The climbing fibers from the inferior olive carry the error signals for learning. In the figure filled circles denote inhibitory synapses and the filled squares denote the excitatory synapse. The error signal is denoted by dotted lines.

3.3.2 Unsupervised learning (UL)

Contrary to supervised learning, unsupervised learning (Fig. 3.3B) does not require a labeled dataset i.e. there is no input-output mapping. Due to the absence of mapping there is no teacher for providing feedback and the model is not informed if the output generated is correct or not. This type of network finds application in (a) determining similarity between a new input and previously encountered data; (b) principal component analysis; (c) finding natural clusters in the input data based on suitable similarity measure; (d) prototyping by forming categories and then outputting an appropriate class (e) encoding the input using least number of bits, i.e., data

compression; and (f) feature mapping to create a topographic map of the input (Hertz *et al.*).

A special case of unsupervised learning is Hebbian learning which states that when two neurons exhibit correlated activity, the synapse that connects them must be strengthened. In the words of Donald Hebb, who first proposed this mechanism as a substrate for learning and memory in his book *The organization of behavior: A neuropsychological theory*, Hebbian learning is described as follows:

“When an axon of cell A is near enough to excite B and repeatedly or persistently takes part in firing it, some growth process or metabolic change takes place in one or both cells such that A's efficiency, as one of the cells firing B, is increased.”

-Hebb (2005)

Hebbian learning has been shown to be able to explain the development of topographic maps in several cortical areas including the somatosensory (Feldman *et al.*, 2005), visual (Masquelier *et al.*, 2007), auditory (Vallabha *et al.*, 2007) and even the motor cortex (Wolters *et al.*, 2003; Hauk *et al.*, 2004).

3.3.3 Reinforcement learning (RL)

“Reinforcement learning is learning what to do--how to map situations to actions--so as to maximize a numerical reward signal.”

- Sutton *et al.* (1998)

The third method (Fig. 3.3C) of motor learning is reinforcement learning (RL). The two main components in RL are the agent and the environment (Fig. 3.5). For a given state (s_t) the agent chooses and executes an action (a_t). This action generates a reward (r_{t+1}) and due to the action taken the state is also updated to s_{t+1} . The overall objective of the task is to maximize the numerical value of reward.

Fig. 3.5: An overview of reinforcement learning. Adapted from *Sutton et al. (1998)*

Biologically, the cortico-basal ganglia circuit (Fig. 3.5) is known to be involved in RL (Doya, 2000; Bar-Gad *et al.*, 2003; Frank *et al.*, 2004b; Sridharan *et al.*, 2006; Doya, 2007; Doya, 2008; Chakravarthy *et al.*, 2010). Schultz *et al.* (1997) demonstrated that dopamine is involved in future reward prediction. If the event is more rewarding than predicted, the dopaminergic neurons increase their firing; if the event is less rewarding than predicted, the firing level dips; and if there is no mismatch between the reward received and predicted, there is no change in firing. Hence, the firing

activity of dopaminergic cells represents the error between the actual and predicted future reward (Schultz *et al.*, 1997; Chakravarthy *et al.*, 2010). In the classical RL literature, the dopamine signal can be correlated to the temporal difference error (TD error) (Sutton *et al.*, 1998; Chakravarthy *et al.*, 2010). The dopaminergic projections from SNc modulate the sensorimotor cortical projections to the striatum (Chakravarthy *et al.*, 2010). One of the interesting features of RL is the absence of an explicit teacher (Chakravarthy *et al.*, 2010). So, the agent is not aware of which actions are more rewarding than others. Thus the agent must learn more rewarding actions through exploration; with rewarding actions being reinforced and non-rewarding/ punitive actions being attenuated (Chakravarthy *et al.*, 2010). If a task requires a sequence of actions for completion and the reward is obtained only at the end of the trial, then the agent estimates a proxy to the reward, *Value* (V). *Value*, which represents the total expected future reward, is used for action selection (Chakravarthy *et al.*, 2010). The *value* is computed by an entity called *Critic* and actions are performed by *Actor* (Chakravarthy *et al.*, 2010). In order to maximize the *value*, the agent can either choose to exploit or explore. Exploitation is the process by which the action which causes the highest increase in Value is chosen. However, continuous exploitation may not help an agent reach an optimal outcome. In such a case, the agent must explore to find possible optimal solution.

RL theory has been applied to model a wide range of motor functions of BG. For example, a computational model for reaching task was presented by Magdoom *et al.* (2011). This model features a two-link arm driven by the motor cortex to reach one of

several distinct targets. Outputs of motor cortex and the BG are combined to move the arm. The distance between the hand and the target is used to construct a *value* function which is computed in striatum. BG noise is the source of the exploratory behavior in early stages of learning. Once the target is reached, the system receives a reward which is used to train the motor cortex for the combined activity of motor cortex and the BG. In the model, the authors also demonstrated the effect of reduced dopamine levels (similar to Parkinson's disease) on tremors, a classical symptom of PD.

One of the key aims of this thesis is to study using computational modeling and experiment precision grip performance in PD patients. Such a model would comprise of a model of BG and a model of precision grip performance. In Chapter 6, we will present a model of BG based on an expanded version of RL framework.

Now we discuss various computational models of precision grip performance.

3.4 PRECISION GRIP MODELS

Various models for precision grip are described individually in the following text.

3.4.1 Kim *et al.* (1994)

Kim *et al.* (1994) studied how humans generate GF by sensing friction force. In their model, under no-slip conditions the GF generated is a function of frictional force. However, to prevent slip, the GF generated must be higher than the slip force. To achieve a GF higher than the slip force, the GF change generated is proportional to the acceleration between the finger and the object. The limitation of this model is that it is not a complete model of a grip/lift task.

3.4.2 de Gruijl *et al.* (2009)

A computational model to generate optimal GF in anticipatory PG tasks was proposed (de Gruijl *et al.*, 2009). The model used the olivo-cerebellar architecture with delayed feedback to replicate the human performance. In this study, information about arm acceleration, arm position, surface texture, slip force and noise is received as inputs by the granule cells which project via excitatory synapses to the Purkinje cells. Purkinje cells inhibit the deep cerebellar nucleus which generates the GF and also inhibits inferior-olive. The error signal, which is the difference between the experimental GF and simulated GF, is fed-back to the granule cells for updating of the state information and also to the inferior-olive. Based on the signals from inferior-olive the synaptic weights of the Purkinje cells are changed. The study, which ignores kinematic changes in the object due to grip force generation, is limited to the anticipatory GF generation.

3.4.3 Ulloa *et al.* (2003)

This study focused on developing a cortical and cerebellum-based computational model for reactive and anticipatory generation of GF using slip information as error signal (Ulloa *et al.*, 2003). The model was subdivided into: 1) arm transport component, which is used to move arm in position to grasp the object; 2) grip aperture component, which regulates the grip aperture; 3) GO component, which represents the signal to initiate movement; 4) slip error component, which represents the slip error; 5) load error component, which determines the load error; and 6) cerebellar component which prevents and corrects the anticipated performance errors. The model generates grip forces dependent on texture and weight of the object. The GF component requires the slip force error to be calculated as a difference between the slip force (which is dependent on weight and texture) and the actual grip force generated. The load force component requires a load force error computation as a difference between adequate load force which is dependent on weight, and the current load force. The study is able to generate higher grip forces for higher object weight and for decreased friction coefficient. However, the model is not accurately able to generate GF profile since the PGF (similar to an overshoot in an under-damped system output), described in numerous experimental studies (Johansson *et al.*, 1984; Johansson *et al.*, 1988a; Johansson *et al.*, 1988b; Forssberg *et al.*, 1991a; Forssberg *et al.*, 1992; Johansson *et al.*, 1992a; Johansson *et al.*, 1992b; Johansson *et al.*, 1994; Forssberg *et al.*, 1995; Flanagan *et al.*, 1997; Flanagan *et al.*, 2006), is absent. The model grip force profile was similar to the over-damped system output without any

overshoot. The interaction of fingers with object and the changes in kinematic parameters were ignored.

3.4.4 Fagergren *et al.* (2000)

Since the GF profile looks similar to the step response of a second order system, Fagergren *et al.* (2000) proposed a second order transfer function $[H(s) = 280 / (s^2 + 22s + 280)]$ for the GF producing system with sensory feedback. In the first part of the study, experiments were conducted on healthy controls to measure the active increase in GF. In this task, the subjects were instructed to increase their GF in a step like manner from initial value of 1%-50% of the maximum voluntary contraction. To measure the reactive component, the object being gripped was suddenly loaded by dropping a weight in the receptacle attached to the grip instrument. The transfer functions obtained for active and reactive control were individually calculated and then combined to obtain the transfer function for the GF generation component which is common to both active and reactive tasks. The study does not explicitly model object dynamics and the interaction of the hand/finger system with the object.

3.4.5 Engeberg (2013)

This study deals with precision grip forces generated while subjects learnt to track a desired trajectory by moving a manipulandum. The study also models change in GF generation with learning. The manipulandum consists of two plates with a provision for placing a spring of different spring constants between them. A visual feedback is

provided for the amount of displacement of the position (1 mm displacement of the plates had 3.54mm displacement on screen). The tasks comprised of matching the user generated trajectories with the desired position trajectories. The first task's visual stimulus was a stepwise increase in trajectory followed by a step decrease. The stimulus in the second task comprised a sequence of step inputs followed by ramps and two sinusoids. The third task comprised only of the step inputs from the second task. The first task was considered as an uninformed task because significant displacement of the plates was not observed and the subject had no information about position mappings and the spring coefficient. The subsequent steps constitute the informed task because the spring constant information was known after the first task. The authors developed separate transfer functions for the uninformed

$$\left(\frac{x_U}{x_D} = \frac{39.75e^{-0.198s}}{s^2 + 0.62s + 39.75} \right) \text{ and the informed tasks } \left(\frac{x_I}{x_D} = \frac{19.31e^{-0.198s}}{s^2 + 5.65s + 19.31} \right).$$

The model changed the adaptive gains from 39.75 (uninformed) to 19.31 (informed). Hence, the system dynamics change and position mapping is learned by manipulandum displacement. The model uses the experimental data to obtain the PID parameters (similar to Fagergren *et al.* (2000)) for the uninformed task and informed task and then adapts the transfer function parameters obtained from uninformed task to informed task. In this model the object dynamics and the interaction of hand/finger system with the object are not explicitly modeled.

3.4.6 Kim *et al.* (2002)

This study presents a controller for robotic fingers for a smooth transfer of the object from human subject to robotic fingers. A human subject controls the grip force by sensing the slip between the finger and the object. The model also featured a similar process wherein the presence of slip, detected using Coulomb friction law, caused the robotic gripper to increase the GF proportional to the slip. The GF generation was also dependent on friction coefficient between the robotic gripper and the object. The system performed smooth handing over of the object.

3.4.7 Fagergren *et al.* (2003)

The model of Fagergren *et al.* (2003) is a significant improvement over the earlier model of Fagergren *et al.* (2000). This model updates the GF based on the sensory feedback received by the controller. Furthermore, the model of Fagergren *et al.* (2003) is a neuro-mechanical model which explicitly models hand-object interaction. The model of Fagergren *et al.* (2003) consists of three components: object, hand and control. The object was assumed to weight 300 g. The model borrows the friction coefficients (static μ for sandpaper surface= 1.21 and static μ for silk surface = 0.35) from Johansson *et al.* (1984) for simulation and experiments. In the simulations the dynamic μ was considered to be 80% of static μ . The control component generates two output signals — the neural GF and neural LF (using target values for GF and LF). The neural GF and neural LF generate GF and LF respectively in the hand.

Using the transfer function described in Fagergren *et al.* (2000), the authors were able to conclude that GF-LF delay is used to prevent slip.

3.5 MODELS OF BASAL GANGLIA

The Basal ganglia system is known for its role in several domains of brain function including motor (Marsden, 1982; Alexander *et al.*, 1989), cognitive (Marsden, 1982), affective (Hamakawa *et al.*, 1998) and even autonomic (Magalhaes *et al.*, 1995; Benedetti *et al.*, 2004). In the motor domain alone, its functions include control of reaching movements (Jaeger *et al.*, 1993; Helie *et al.*, 2013), gait (Garcia-Rill, 1986; Hausdorff *et al.*, 1998; Helie *et al.*, 2013), speech (Speedie *et al.*, 1993), eye saccades (Alexander *et al.*, 1989; Hikosaka *et al.*, 2000; Helie *et al.*, 2013), handwriting (Phillips *et al.*, 1991; Gangadhar *et al.*, 2009; Helie *et al.*, 2013), posture (Mink, 1996; Plotnik *et al.*, 2011; Helie *et al.*, 2013) and precision grip (Ingvarsson *et al.*, 1997; Fellows *et al.*, 1998; Fellows *et al.*, 2004). In the cognitive domain, its contributions to working memory (Berns *et al.*, 1998; Monchi *et al.*, 2000), sequence generation (Miyachi *et al.*, 1997; Berns *et al.*, 1998) and decision making (Berns *et al.*, 1996; Frank *et al.*, 2006; Bogacz *et al.*, 2007) are well-known. Therefore impairment in BG is associated with several neurological disorders like Parkinson's disease (Bernheimer *et al.*, 1973; Marsden, 1982; Rafal *et al.*, 1984; Carlsson *et al.*, 1990; Obeso *et al.*, 2000) and Huntington's disease (Bernheimer *et al.*, 1973; Marsden, 1982; Carlsson *et al.*, 1990; Obeso *et al.*, 2000), and neuropsychiatric disorders like schizophrenia (Carlsson *et al.*, 1990; Ring *et al.*, 2002).

As described earlier in chapter 2, BG is a group of 7 highly interconnected sub-cortical nuclei. These nuclei are arranged in two distinct pathways— the direct pathway (DP) and the indirect pathway (IP) (Albin *et al.*, 1989). The activation of DP facilitates the movement, and hence known as Go pathway, while the activation of IP inhibits movement and therefore referred to as the NoGo pathway (Schultz *et al.*, 1997; Schultz, 2010). The activity of the DP and IP is modulated by the neurotransmitter, dopamine (DA), released by the dopaminergic projections from Substantia Nigra pars compacta to the striatum (Kandel *et al.*, 2000b). Various studies have explored the role of altered activations of DP and IP in various movements disorders (DeLong *et al.*, 2007). Over activity of the IP leads to hypokinetic conditions like the akinetic rigidity of PD and under activity of the IP leads to hyperkinetic disorders like chorea and hemiballism (Kandel *et al.*, 2000b).

Hence, the direct and indirect pathways of BG play a complementary role in facilitating or inhibiting the movements (Albin *et al.*, 1989; DeLong, 1990). The DP-IP complementarity also explained aspects of limb movements (Mink, 1996) and saccades (Hikosaka *et al.*, 2000).

To the above picture a new component was added (Wickens *et al.*, 1993) which suggested that the striatum has cellular level mechanisms for setting up competition among the medium spiny neurons (MSNs). Competition is an important feature of action selection in BG (Wickens *et al.*, 1993). The notion of competitive dynamics among striatal neurons led to the emergence of a line of modeling work that described

action selection function of the basal ganglia (Gurney *et al.*, 2001a; Gurney *et al.*, 2001b; Prescott, 2007). The action selection then was developed on slightly different lines by Frank and colleagues who depict the direct and indirect pathways as the Go and NoGo pathways, in recognition of their facilitatory and inhibitory functions (O'Reilly *et al.*, 2006).

Experiments performed by Schultz and colleagues on mesencephalic dopamine neural activity paved the way for major developments in BG modeling approaches (Schultz *et al.*, 1997; Schultz, 2010). In their study, the authors found that the DA cell firing in ventral tegmental area (VTA) had a very strong resemblance to the Temporal Difference (TD) error of the Reinforcement Learning theory (Schultz *et al.*, 1997; Sutton *et al.*, 1998). The striking resemblance between DA cell activity and TD error led to application of RL concepts to the BG function. As described earlier in section on RL theory, the state is the stimulus and action taken is the response to the stimulus. The stimulus-response (S-R) relationships form the very backbone of the RL theory. The S-R relationship is modulated based on reward/punishment feedback from the environment (Chakravarthy *et al.*, 2010). Rewarding relationships resulting in rewards are reinforced and the punitive ones are undermined (Chakravarthy *et al.*, 2010). In many cases, reward arrives after a delay i.e. at the end of the task/trial. The RL agent must, thus, devise a mechanism to identify correct actions during the trial that will lead to reward maximization at the end of the task/trial. This is done through a surrogate to reward, value, which is computed Critic. The RL component performing

action is known as Actor. Application of RL concepts to BG have resulted in a whole class of Actor-Critic models of the basal ganglia (Joel *et al.*, 2002).

In case of an n-arm bandit problem (for a detailed description on n-arm bandit problem refer (Sutton *et al.*, 1998)), repeated sampling will determine which of the arms will be more rewarding than others (Sutton *et al.*, 1998). In such a case, based on the prior knowledge of the reward each yield the subject may “exploit” by choosing the most rewarding arm (eqn.(3.4)) (Sutton *et al.*, 1998). Thus the exploitation process is known as greedy approach (Sutton *et al.*, 1998). If the arm chosen is suboptimal then in long run exploiting the same arm may lead to lower rewards (Sutton *et al.*, 1998). To overcome this limitation of the greedy policy, a ϵ -greedy policy was introduced (Sutton *et al.*, 1998). In ϵ -greedy policy, during exploitation, the agent will take a random action (explore) with a small probability ϵ (Sutton *et al.*, 1998). On the contrary, if the subject chooses some arm other than the most rewarding arm, the subject is “exploring” (Sutton *et al.*, 1998).

$$Q_t(a^*) = \max_a Q_t(a) \tag{3.4}$$

where, value of action (a) at trial (t), is given by $Q_t(a)$.

Using the simple ϵ -greedy policy seems an excellent choice but it suffers from one major drawback, that during exploration all the arms are considered equal for

exploration. A workaround to this problem is using *softmax* action, where all the actions are ranked and weighted as per their probability estimates $P_t(a)$ (eqn.(3.5)).

$$P_t(a) = \frac{e^{Q_t(a)/\tau}}{\sum_{b=1}^n e^{Q_t(b)/\tau}} \quad (3.5)$$

here, τ is temperature, high values of τ cause all actions to weigh equally and low τ cause a greater difference in selection probability for actions.

In order to reconcile the RL theory with the BG functionality, using fMRI, O'Doherty *et al.* (2004) identified the neural substrates for RL in brain. It was found that the dorsal striatum played the role of Actor whereas the ventral striatum served as Critic (O'Doherty *et al.*, 2004). Interestingly, in this study no neural substrates were identified for exploration in basal ganglia (O'Doherty *et al.*, 2004). Chakravarthy and colleagues suggested that the IP, containing the STN-GPe loop, is the substrate of exploration in BG (Chakravarthy *et al.*, 2010). This hypothesis was used to describe a host of BG functions (Chakravarthy *et al.*, 2010; Krishnan *et al.*, 2011; Magdoom *et al.*, 2011; Kalva *et al.*, 2012; Sukumar *et al.*, 2012).

Thus we have a highly effective modeling approach to the basal ganglia based on RL framework. But it must be noted that all the aforementioned approaches to the basal ganglia modeling constitute the Value function. There exists a generalization of the

Value function, known as the Utility function, which is better suited to cases when reward delivery is stochastic. The Utility function is a linear combination of two quantities—Value and Risk—where Risk is defined as the reward variance (Kahneman, 1979).

Let us consider a small illustration to demonstrate how risk plays a role in decision making. Consider an example (Fig. 3.6) which requires the subject to move a cursor from the Start position, located in zero rewarding zone (ZZ), to the rewarding zone (RZ) the avoiding a highly penalizing zone (PZ). A “value only” approach will cause the cursor to just cross the RZ boundary and stop. A small perturbation can send back the cursor in ZZ zone and thus no reward would be obtained. On addition of time constraint to complete task, the accuracy decreases due to speed-accuracy tradeoff (Trommershauser *et al.*, 2003; Nagengast *et al.*, 2011). In such a scenario, the optimal reaching target should be to move away from the PZ-RZ boundary and ZZ-RZ boundary. Experimentally it was seen that the subjects stay away from the two boundaries (Trommershauser *et al.*, 2003). The final position where the subject stops the cursor is dependent on the value of punishment (Trommershauser *et al.*, 2003). Operating away from reward-punishment or reward-no reward boundary may be considered a strategy for minimizing risk.

Fig. 3.6: Illustration of the task which requires cursor movement from the start position located in zero-reward zone (ZZ) to the rewarding zone (RZ) by avoiding the penalty zone (PZ). The numbers in black represent the reward (if the number is positive) or punishment (if the number is negative) received depending on the position where the cursor stops. Adapted from Trommershauser *et al.* (2003).

We would like to point out that the above illustration is analogous to the problem of precision grip performance. Note that the objective of PGLT is to precision grip-lift the object to the desired height without letting the object slip. Here successful lift is the reward and a failed lift yields no reward. The reward-no reward boundary in PGLT is the F_{crit} . A GF value below F_{crit} prevents the lift completion. Hence, operating sufficiently away from F_{crit} may be considered a decision making strategy for minimizing risk. This need to operate far from the risk boundary, by using a grip force that is considerably larger than F_{crit} , suggests that risk based decision making is probably involved in grip force generation.

Each of the models of basal ganglia described above use value function for action selection (Krishnan *et al.*, 2011; Magdoom *et al.*, 2011; Kalva *et al.*, 2012; Sukumar *et al.*, 2012; Muralidharan *et al.*, 2014), which may be appropriate since they deal with problems without risk. However, for modeling tasks that involve safety margin, it appears that a decision making framework containing both value and risk is more appropriate.

Recently, Balasubramani *et al.* (2014) described a utility based model of the basal ganglia system that explains the role of that system in risk-based decision making and punishment learning. Trommershauser *et al.* (2003) demonstrated that the motor behavior optimizes expected gains. Zhang *et al.* (2010) suggested that utility is maximized during planning of the routes in a terrain with different costs per unit distance covered.

Based on the above mentioned findings, in chapter 6, a model of risk based decision making in reinforcement learning framework for a precision grip task in healthy controls and PD patients is presented.

To summarize, among the models of precision grip performance reviewed above, there are very few models that study precision grip in the full control loop which includes hand-object interaction. Many of the models are abstract behavioral models that meet the experiment at the input/output level. Among the models that investigate neural substrates there are models that consider the contributions of motor cortex and

cerebellum but none that consider the contributions of basal ganglia to human grip force generation. Moreover, none of the PG studies present a model for PD which forms the motivation for the present thesis.

In the overall schema to understand and develop a computational model for PG force changes in Parkinson's patients, we first need a model which explains the GF under transient change in friction (keeping all the other variables like weight, size, and surface curvature constant). Further, we need to propose training mechanisms involved in training the model parameters. After obtaining a well performing model, we will modify it to accommodate the risk based decision making. In Chapter 1 we have said that loss of dopaminergic cells in the SNc (a key entity of BG) cause PD. In Chapter 2 we have discussed that BG is involved in regulating the various aspects of the GF generation. So, the computational model developed must include BG and the model parameters must be learned using reinforcement learning. Limiting the amount of dopamine available will simulate PD OFF condition (PD patient not on medication) and addition of a small amount of dopamine will simulate the PD ON (PD patients on medication). The simulation results are then compared to the experimental results.

In the following Chapter, a study on the human grip performance under variable skin conditions is presented. This study deals with the variation of GFs generated by subjects when their hands are not artificially wet (dry) and on saturating the fingertip with water. A computational model is also proposed which generates GF profiles and training mechanism for the same is also described.

CHAPTER 4

PRECISION GRIP MODEL FRAMEWORK

In this chapter we present a computational model for a grip-lift task. The model consists of a feedback control system in which a cuboidal object is gripped and lifted in the vertical direction. Two fingers (thumb and index finger) apply horizontal GF, of equal magnitude and opposite sign, on the object. The fingers also apply a LF mediated by the friction of the skin-object interface. The control is mediated by two PID controllers one generating GF and the other generating LF. The controllers are trained using genetic algorithm to lift an object of a given weight to a desired height. The model described in the present chapter is used in the following chapter to study the role of skin friction on PG performance. In chapter 6, a small variation of the model is coupled with a model of BG. The combined PG model and BG model is then used to simulate impairment in precision grip in PD patients.

Note that the grip force and lift force are mathematically denoted as F_G and F_L , respectively. These two should not be confused with GF and LF which are abbreviations of grip force and lift force, respectively.

4.1 MODEL

In order to perform a PGLT, the thumb and the index finger must grip the object and generate two forces —grip force (F_G) and lift force (F_L) (see Fig. 4.1). As the name indicates, the F_G is the force which is used to grip the object and F_L is the force which lifts the object. F_G couples the fingers to the object. Higher F_G is necessary to prevent the object from slipping. Due to finger-object coupling and the friction which exists between the finger and the object, a frictional force (F_f) is developed. Since there are two surfaces where the fingers make contact with the object, each finger generates a frictional force of $F_f/2$. Friction inhibits relative motion between the finger and the object. Therefore when finger is lifted by F_L , with sufficiently large F_G , the object also lifts. Before the starting of the lift, the object is rested on the table. While the object is contact with the table, a normal force (F_n) perpendicular to the table surface is generated. Since the fingers cannot be massless, weight of the fingers ($M_{fin} g$) must also be included in the model.

Fig. 4.1: Free body diagram showing forces acting on finger and object.

Using the above mentioned principles a free body diagram for finger and object was constructed (Fig. 4.1). The finger-object interaction model along with the kinematic (discussed separately later in the text) parameters comprise the plant. The input to the plant is two forces (F_G and F_L) and output consists of kinematic parameters like position, velocity and acceleration of both the object and fingers.

The two input forces F_G and F_L are generated by F_G controller and F_L controller, respectively (for the system overview see Fig. 4.2). It is known from experimental precision grip studies, that though F_G and F_L are simultaneously generated (Forsberg *et al.*, 1991a; Johansson *et al.*, 1994) they have distinct neural substrates in the brain (Ehrsson *et al.*, 2001; Ehrsson *et al.*, 2003). In the model, the two forces F_L and F_G are generated by two independent controllers. These controllers take kinematic parameters as the inputs and generate forces as output, which in turn act on the plant and produce change in kinematic parameters. Fig. 4.2 represents the overview of the model showing the two controllers and the plant in closed loop configuration.

Fig. 4.2: The overview of the model for grip force (F_G) and lift force (F_L) generation.

Now let us discuss the individual components of the model in detail.

4.2 CONTROLLERS

In the current model the F_L and F_G controllers are considered to be Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) controllers (similar to the precision grip model of (Fagergren *et al.*, 2000)). The controller parameters PID_{KL} (for F_L controller) and PID_{KG} (for F_G controller) consist of three terms each: the proportionality term (K_P) for present error; Integrative term (K_I) for accumulation of past errors; and derivative term (K_D) for prediction of future errors. Throughout the text subscript ‘L’ denotes the lift force parameter and ‘G’ means the grip force parameter.

4.2.1 F_L controller

The F_L controller generates the lift force for lifting the fingers up. The controller with PID parameters PID_{KL} receives input error (E_L) as the input and generates F_L as the output. E_L (eqn.(4.1)) is a position error which is the difference between the current position (X_o) and the reference position (X_{ref}).

$$E_L = X_{ref} - X_o \quad (4.1)$$

The force output of the F_L controller is given in eqn.(4.2).

$$F_{L,PID} = K_{P,L} E_L + K_{I,L} \int_0^t E_L(\tau) d\tau + K_{D,L} \frac{dE_L}{dt} \quad (4.2)$$

In typical experimental studies on PGLT (Johansson *et al.*, 1984; Westling *et al.*, 1984b; Johansson *et al.*, 1988a; Forssberg *et al.*, 1991b; Gordon *et al.*, 1991; Forssberg *et al.*, 1992; Gordon *et al.*, 1992; Eliasson *et al.*, 1995; Forssberg *et al.*, 1995; Jenmalm *et al.*, 1998; Saels *et al.*, 1999), the F_L increases from initial zero value to a steady state. However, the PID output is finite for an input. Hence, the use of eqn. (4.2) in F_L generation would give rise to discontinuous, initial increase in forces which is unrealistic. In order to prevent this discontinuous rise in force, first order dynamics was used to produce smoothened F_L (eqn. (4.3)) from $F_{L,PID}$:

$$\tau_{F,L} \frac{dF_L}{dt} = -F_L + F_{L,PID} \quad (4.3)$$

4.2.2 F_G controller

F_G is generated by F_G controller, a PID controller. The PID parameters (PID_{KG}) and the input error (E_G) determine the output (F_G) of the controller. The input error to the F_G controller is the square of the difference between the velocities of the finger (dX_{fin}/dt) and the object (dX_o/dt). This is chosen to reflect slip. In case of an insufficient F_G a slip will occur. This will send a non-zero input to the controller which will increase the F_G . When encountering a slip, (irrespective of its sign) the grip force must be increased to prevent slip. Hence the error term consists of squared velocity difference (eqn.(4.4)).

$$E_G = \left(\frac{dX_{fin}}{dt} - \frac{dX_o}{dt} \right)^2 \quad (4.4)$$

It was observed that when using E_G defined as in eqn.(4.4) directly in the control loop, very high controller outputs were obtained, which destabilized the system. Hence, E_G was smoothed using the first order dynamics (eqn.(4.5)) and use it to define E_G instead of eqn.(4.4).

$$\tau_{E,G} \frac{dE_G}{dt} = -E_G + \left(\frac{dX_{fin}}{dt} - \frac{dX_o}{dt} \right)^2 \quad (4.5)$$

The force output generated for F_G controller is given in eqn.(4.6).

$$F_{G,PID} = K_{P,G} E_G + K_{I,G} \int_0^t E_G(\tau) d\tau + K_{D,G} \frac{dE_G}{dt} \quad (4.6)$$

Note that F_G controller output, F_G (eqn.(4.6)), is a nonlinear function of the input state, as it involves a quadratic function of slip, E_G (eqn.(4.5)). Therefore, F_G increases with increased slip, irrespective of the sign of the slip.

Similar to eqn.(4.3), first order dynamics was used to produce smoothed F_G (eqn. (4.7)) from $F_{G,PID}$ respectively:

$$\tau_{F,G} \frac{dF_G}{dt} = -F_G + F_{G,PID} \quad (4.7)$$

Since all the trials have initial force values of zero so at the beginning of every trial, F_G and F_L were initialized to 0 at the beginning of trials.

4.3 FINGER - OBJECT INTERACTION MODEL (PLANT)

The plant receives the inputs (F_L and F_G) from the controllers and calculates the kinematic parameters. The F_L and F_G are coupled to the object through friction. A subtle feature of finger-object interaction in PG is that both F_L and F_G act at the interface between fingers and the object, obscuring the fact that the two forces have very different origins: F_G is generated by the muscles of the index finger and thumb while F_L could be arising from the muscles of the wrist and/or elbow. In this study, we assume a simple scenario in which F_L acts on the finger and lifts it; F_G presses the finger to the object and couples it to the object. In this simplified representation, the “finger” may be thought to actually represent the part of the hand (thumb and index finger) that interacted with the object.

The net forces acting on finger (F_{fin}) and object (F_o) are given as:

$$F_{fin} = F_L - F_f - M_{fin}g \quad (4.8)$$

$$F_o = F_f + F_n - M_o g \quad (4.9)$$

where, F_f is the frictional force, M_{fin} is the mass of the finger, g is the acceleration due to gravity, F_n is the normal force and M_o is the mass of the object.

The F_f takes the value of F_{slip} (eqn.(4.10)) under ‘slip’ condition.

$$F_{slip} = 2\mu F_G \quad (4.10)$$

Under the condition when the F_G is sufficiently large the F_f is equivalent to F_{noslip} . The F_{noslip} (eqn.(4.11)) is determined by assuming the finger and object move together i.e. their velocities and accelerations are equal ($a_{fin} = a_o$).

$$\begin{aligned} a_{fin} = a_o &\Leftrightarrow \frac{F_{fin}}{M_{fin}} = \frac{F_o}{M_o} \\ \Rightarrow \frac{F_L}{M_{fin}} - \frac{F_{noslip}}{M_{fin}} - \frac{M_{fin}g}{M_{fin}} &= \frac{F_{noslip}}{M_o} + \frac{F_n}{M_o} - \frac{M_o g}{M_o} \\ \Rightarrow \frac{F_L}{M_{fin}} - \frac{F_{noslip}}{M_{fin}} &= \frac{F_{noslip}}{M_o} + \frac{F_n}{M_o} \\ F_{noslip} &= \frac{M_o M_{fin}}{M_o + M_{fin}} \left(\frac{F_L}{M_{fin}} - \frac{F_n}{M_o} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (4.11)$$

The F_f calculation is based on the maximum frictional force that can be generated and the frictional force required to prevent the slip. Frictional force, F_f and normal force, F_n are given in eqns. (4.12) and eqn. (4.13) below:

$$F_f = \begin{cases} F_{noslip}, & \text{if } F_{noslip} < F_{slip} \\ F_{slip}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4.12)$$

$$F_n = \begin{cases} M_o g - F_f, & \text{if } X_o = 0 \wedge M_o g > F_f \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4.13)$$

The forces acting on the object (eqn. (4.14)) and the finger (eqn. (4.15)) are computed using Newton's second law of motion.

$$F_o = M_o \frac{d^2 X_o}{dt^2} \quad (4.14)$$

$$F_{fin} = M_{fin} \frac{d^2 X_{fin}}{dt^2} \quad (4.15)$$

4.3.1 Determining controller parameters

At this stage, the model has 9 parameters namely $K_{P,L}$, $K_{I,L}$, $K_{D,L}$, $K_{P,G}$, $K_{I,G}$, $K_{D,G}$, $\tau_{F,G}$, $\tau_{E,G}$ and $\tau_{F,L}$. For determining these parameters we need some objective function which can characterize the performance of the PG system. Since we have two controllers in the model, training them simultaneously poses a significant challenge. We therefore look for the possibility of training the two controllers independently. For sufficiently high F_G , under no slip conditions, the F_G controller has no effect on the object, which then moves completely under the influence of the F_L controller. Therefore, by keeping F_G sufficiently high (10 N), first the F_L controller is trained, so that the model becomes independent of the F_G controller (equivalent of no slip

condition). Then the objective function C_L (eqn.(4.16)), which contains various position errors, is minimized. The main intent behind the formulation of C_L as in eqn. (4.16) was to find F_L that would minimize position error, which was represented by the second term on RHS of eqn.(4.16). The first term, standard deviation in position, σ_X , was necessary to suppress undesirable fluctuation in position even after the arm had reached the reference position. The third term on the RHS of eqn. (4.16) was necessary to suppress unwanted overshoot in position, which was observed in simulations without this term.

$$C_L = \sigma_X + \frac{|\bar{X}_{O,M} - X_{ref}|}{X_{ref}} + \frac{|\max(X_{O,M}) - X_{ref}|}{X_{ref}} \quad (4.16)$$

where, C_L is the cost function for training the F_L controller, σ_X is the standard deviation of the object position, $\bar{X}_{O,M}$ is the mean object position between 3500 - 4500 ms obtained from the model, X_{ref} is the reference position.

After training the parameters for F_L controller the F_G controller parameters are trained using the F_G objective function C_G (eqn. (4.17)). This objective function matches the various simulated and experimental parameters and it also includes a slip minimization term. The idea behind formulation of C_G as in eqn. (4.17) was to produce a grip profile that matches the experimental profile closely. To that end, we include error in PGF and SGF in C_G . The last term on the RHS of eqn. (4.17) is included to reduce the slip. (The subscripts M and E refer to ‘model’ and ‘experiment’ respectively).

$$C_G = \frac{|PGF_M - PGF_E|}{PGF_E} + \frac{|SGF_M - SGF_E|}{SGF_E} + |X_o - X_{fin}| \quad (4.17)$$

where, C_G is the cost function for F_G controller, PGF_M is the PGF obtained from the model, PGF_E is the experimental PGF, SGF_M is the SGF obtained from the model, and SGF_E is the experimental SGF.

A single simulated trial consisted of the simulation of the model for 5s of simulated time with step interval =0.001s. The PID parameters, PID_{KL} and PID_{KG} , were trained using genetic algorithm (GA) (Goldberg, 1989; Whitley, 1994). Each individual solution is represented by a trial and the corresponding cost function (C_L/C_G for PID_{KL}/PID_{KG}) was determined. The GA parameters used in training are the number of individuals (= 100), maximum number of generations (= 1000) and elite count (= 4).

The model described in this chapter will be used in the following chapter to simulate human PG performance under variable skin friction conditions.

CHAPTER 5

PRECISION GRIP PERFORMANCE UNDER VARIABLE SKIN FRICTION CONDITIONS.

5.1 INTRODUCTION

In the previous chapter, a modeling framework for the PGBT is presented. This model is used in present chapter to simulate the experimentally obtained grip force changes due to wetting (from normal dry condition) in subjects with high friction and low friction. The classification of the subjects in high friction and low friction is based on the friction coefficient in dry condition. In this chapter we also observe the effect of partial and full training of the model parameters when the friction between the finger and the object is reduced due to wetting.

As discussed in Chapter 2, PG is the ability to hold and dexterously manipulate a small object held between index finger and thumb (Napier, 1956). Many studies focus on the force generation mechanism (Forssberg *et al.*, 1991b) and physical characteristics affecting the PGLT (Johansson *et al.*, 1984; Westling *et al.*, 1984b; Johansson *et al.*, 1988a; Forssberg *et al.*, 1991b; Gordon *et al.*, 1991; Forssberg *et al.*, 1992; Gordon *et al.*, 1992; Eliasson *et al.*, 1995; Forssberg *et al.*, 1995; Jenmalm *et al.*, 1998; Saels *et al.*, 1999). However, it is possible to regulate the object properties

like weight, size, texture and surface curvature by using the same object for all the trials. Now the grip force developed is only dependent on the friction coefficient (and not on the texture (Johansson *et al.*, 1984)) between the hand and the object.

Many studies focus on the effect of altered friction between finger-object interface and its effect on PG performance (Johansson *et al.*, 1984; Westling *et al.*, 1984b; Forssberg *et al.*, 1995; Saels *et al.*, 1999; Andre *et al.*, 2009; Andre *et al.*, 2010). In some of these studies, (Johansson *et al.*, 1984; Westling *et al.*, 1984b; Forssberg *et al.*, 1992) the surface of the object was altogether modified by using materials like sandpaper/ suede/ silk (Johansson *et al.*, 1984; Johansson *et al.*, 1994; Ingvarsson *et al.*, 1997; Johansson, 1998), talc (Saels *et al.*, 1999) or water (Andre *et al.*, 2010). In a study on hydration levels affecting the GF performance, Andre *et al.* (2009) lumped all the subjects together. This lumping of all the subjects together prevented the authors to observe the effect of intrinsic friction coefficient (when the skin is not artificially hydrated) on grip force generation. In another study, Andre *et al.* (2010) dealt with horizontal point-to-point reaching task with the object held in precision grip. The task given to the subjects was more complicated than pure grip-lift task as there are sharp movements when the desired target changes.

The GF is dependent on friction between the finger and the object but not on the texture (Cadoret *et al.*, 1996). Before the information about actual friction coefficient is made (available during the lifting process), an estimate of the friction is made based on the texture of the object (Flanagan *et al.*, 1995). This suggests that the information

about the inherent friction i.e. between the fingers to various surfaces is stored and recalled. Based on the friction between the fingers and the object, the subjects can be classified into intrinsically high skin friction subjects and intrinsically low friction subjects. Their grip force performance can then be evaluated under intrinsic friction and upon acute change in friction due to wetting.

In the present study, the role of individual variation in skin friction on PG performance is investigated. The subjects were classified either as “high skin friction” or “low skin friction” based on their intrinsic friction coefficient. Then the change in PG performance, brought about by changing the friction coefficient by wetting of the fingers in water, was measured. The change in the skin friction due to wetting is a complex process. However, in the present study, an identical method was used to change the friction for all subjects, hence the study does not require understanding the details of evolution of skin friction due to wetting. In summary, this study focuses on the contrasting changes in PG performance due to intrinsic (due to inherent friction coefficient) and acute changes (due to wetting) in friction, using modelling and experiment.

5.2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Test object: A custom made object (dimensions 37x50x70 mm; mass 0.117 kg) was constructed using Plexiglas. The object was fitted with a load cell for measuring GF with four strain gauges mounted on a steel plate in bridge configuration. The load cell

output was amplified to a range between 0-20N and was conditioned using 16 Hz low pass filter (for calibration details see Fig. 5.1). The data was digitized at 1 KHz using PCI 6014 National Instruments data acquisition card. For data acquisition LABVIEWTM 8 was used and for analysis MATLAB[®] 7 was used.

Fig. 5.1: Calibration curve for input load and output voltage for FG strain gauge. The equation for trend line is $Output = 0.0018 Load + 0.074$; $R^2=0.9979$.

A metallic enclosure with a height of 30 cm was placed around the object. The reference position ($X_{ref} = 0.12$ m) was marked on the metallic enclosure. The enclosure did not interfere with the lifting process. A touchpad (containing a switch)

was provided which marked the lift onset (on palm removal) and lift completion (on palm replacement). It also served as a platform for resting the hand between lifts. The object was loaded by placing a mass in the slot on the top of the object. The total mass of the object (M_0) with 0.013 kg load was 0.130 kg (1.274 N).

5.3 SUBJECTS AND PROCEDURE

In this study 16 healthy (12 male, 4 female) right-handed subjects with 35.94 (\pm 8.80) mean (\pm SD) age and range 26 to 53 years participated. The study was explained to the subjects and their informed written consent was taken in their native language. The study was approved by the Institutional Review Board, Christian Medical College, Vellore, India.

5.3.1 Dry condition

Dry condition means that the finger surface was not artificially changed using either water or artificial drying. In this task the subjects operate at their intrinsic friction. Each of the subjects who participated in the study washed his/her hands with soap and tap water. The hands were then air dried (for $>$ 2 minutes to prevent the μ variation during trials (Johansson *et al.*, 1984)) until visible traces of water were evaporated. The subject was then asked to sit in a chair in a comfortable position with his/her hand flexed in the anterior direction. On the verbal instruction given by the experimenter the subject lifted his/her hand off the touch pad, approached the object, gripped the object and lifted it to a height of 12 cm above the table without tilting the object. Once

the object is held in the stable grip force for 6 seconds, the subject was verbally instructed to gradually decrease the GF and let the object slip from the grip. The hand was replaced on the touchpad, the palm lift off from touchpad and its replacement on the table conclude a single trial. After a time interval of 10s subject was asked to perform the trail again. After each trial the object was returned to its original position. The object's gripping surfaces were cleaned with dry tissue paper to maintain uniformity in conditions. Each subject performed six consecutive trials for a load force of 1.274 N.

The dry task was preceded by the training for the lifting task so that the subjects were able to lift the object at an approximately constant rate and the PGF and SGF were almost constant, this is to maintain uniformity among subjects.

5.3.2 Wet condition

In the wetting condition the procedure for task remains same as that of the dry condition with the exception of wetting of the fingers by dipping them in water at room temperature before each trial. In the wetting condition the subjects were not allowed to wash their hand with soap and water after the completion of the dry task, prior to the wet task and no training was provided. The procedure for the wet condition is as follows: The subject was then asked to sit in a chair in a comfortable position with his/her hand flexed in the anterior direction. The subject was asked to dip fingers involved in precision gripping (index finger and thumb) in distilled water

for 30 seconds at room temperature for saturating the fingertips with water. Trial begins with verbal command of the experimenter followed by immersing the finger in distilled water for 2 seconds. This was followed by removal of hand from touchpad, approaching the object, gripping it in precision grip and lifting it to a height of 12 cm without tilting. Once the object is held in the stable grip force for 6 seconds, the subject was verbally instructed to gradually decrease the GF and let the object slip from the fingers. The hand was returned to the touch pad, the palm lift-off from touchpad marks the beginning of the trial and palm replacement on the table concludes a single trial. After a time interval of 10s the subject was asked to perform the trial again. After each trial the object surfaces were cleaned with dry tissue paper to maintain uniformity in conditions. The subjects performed six consecutive trials for a load force of 1.274 N. During the entire procedure the subjects were not allowed to wipe or dry the fingers. The experimental wet condition is very similar to the wet condition reported by Andre *et al.* (2009).

5.3.3 Estimating skin friction, μ

In the task when the subject was asked to reduce the grip force gradually, it was to determine the grip force at which the object slips from the grip also referred to as the slip force (F_{crit}). Individual trial friction coefficient was determined for dry and wet conditions using the standard slip force-load force method (Forsberg *et al.*, 1995) (eqn.(5.1)).

$$\mu = \frac{M_o g}{2F_{crit}} \quad (5.1)$$

An average of six consecutive trials (for each condition) was used to determine the average μ for the subject for the dry/ wet condition. Based on the friction coefficient obtained for the dry case the subjects were either classified as high friction or low friction subjects. This classification was based on the k-means clustering, performed on the dry friction coefficient (μ_d) data, into two groups. Those subjects with $\mu_d > 0.805$ were classified as high μ subjects and those with $\mu_d < 0.805$ as low μ subjects. The cluster centres were 0.64 and 0.97; spread = 0.096 and 0.032 respectively. The mean of the two cluster centres (0.805) was taken as classification threshold.

5.4 MODEL

The model used for this study is described in Chapter 4.

One of the key questions addressed in this modeling study was to find out whether PG control strategies were carried over from dry skin case (higher friction) to wet skin (lower friction) case. Therefore, PID parameters were first trained under dry skin conditions, and then were used as initial values for training under wet skin conditions. In the dry case, controller parameters were trained in two stages: PID_{KL} was trained first, followed by $PID_{KG,dry}$. In contrast, for the wet case only $PID_{KG,wet}$ was trained. Note that the plant is nonlinear only because of frictional dynamics. Under ‘no-slip’ condition, which happens in presence of sufficiently strong F_G , the control problem

reduces to simple position control of a mass. Therefore, keeping F_G constant at 10 N ($F_{crit}= 0.637$ N for $\mu=1$ and $F_{crit}= 1.274$ N for $\mu=0.5$), was sufficient to achieve ‘no slip’. Under such conditions PID_{KL} was trained independent of $PID_{KG,dry}$. The best result obtained for PID_{KL} was used in the second stage to train $PID_{KG,dry}$. The initial runs for $PID_{KG,dry}$ showed that the optimal F_G profile could be obtained keeping $K_D=9$, $\tau_{F,G} = 0.06$ and $\tau_{E,G} =0.8$. Hence, these parameters were kept constant and only K_P and K_I were trained for determining the $PID_{KG,dry}$ and $PID_{KG,wet}$ parameters.

For $PID_{KG,wet}$ determination, we kept the PID_{KL} constant across the two conditions (dry/wet) and $PID_{KG,wet}$ was obtained by two training methods. The first method of training involved fully training of the parameters where out of 100 individuals, 50 individuals were initialized as $PID_{KG,dry} \pm \text{noise}$ and 50 were random (with K_P and K_I ranging between $[0,1000]$), this formed the initial range. The elite count was kept constant at 4 and maximum number of generations was kept constant at 1000. The noise added was between $[-200, +200]$. The simulation terminated if the cumulative change in the fitness function was less than 10^{-6} for 50 generations. In the second stage of training (for wet conditions) only partial training of the $PID_{KG,wet}$ was carried out. In this case only 20 individuals ($PID_{KG,dry} \pm \text{noise}$) were used. The elite count was kept constant at 4 and noise added was between $[-200, +200]$. In the wet case, to simulate partial training we changed the maximum number of generations to 5 (compared to 50 generations at which the GA typically terminates for $PID_{KG,dry}$ condition). Reducing the maximum number of generations and individuals drastically reduced the computational time. Training for $PID_{KG,wet}$ was also carried out using GA

(Goldberg, 1989; Whitley, 1994). Advantages of using GA are that, it does not suffer from the problem of local minima, and works for continuous as well as discontinuous fitness functions (Goldberg, 1989). However, GA suffers from high computation time, poor convergence and, in some cases, optimal solution may not be obtained. These limitations are usually overcome by defining a smaller state space, defining the fitness function properly and exploiting the inherently parallel nature of the GA (Goldberg, 1989; Whitley, 1994).

Fig. 5.2: Single trial illustration for (a) S2 and (b) S15. The left (right) images are dry (wet) trials. Horizontal bar shows the duration over which SGF is calculated. Published in (Gupta *et al.*, In press).

5.4.1 PGF and SGF calculation

Each simulation trial lasts for 5 seconds. PGF was calculated as the maximum of F_G in the first 1000 ms after the lift onset. SGF was calculated as the average F_G exerted between 3500 ms and 4500 ms after the lift onset. Fig. 5.2 shows F_G profiles for experimental data (1 trial) for two random subjects (S2 and S15) under dry and wet conditions.

5.5 RESULTS

This study involved both experimental study and a supporting computational study. All the physical properties (weight, size and surface curvature) pertaining to the test object were kept constant and the variation in the data were only due to the difference in friction coefficient. Each of the results is discussed in separate subsections.

5.5.1 Experimental task

All the sixteen subjects that participated in this study showed a decrease in μ on wetting the finger (Table 1). It is found that the intrinsic μ (μ under dry condition) is 0.64 ± 0.13 (for low μ subjects) and 0.97 ± 0.07 (for high μ subjects) ($p < 0.001$). For the dry-wet transition the μ changes to 0.41 ± 0.08 (for low μ subjects) and 0.46 ± 0.11 (for high μ subjects) $p < 0.001$. Two way ANOVA suggested a significant effect of both intrinsic friction [$F(1,28) = 29.5$, $p < 0.001$] and dry-wet transition [$F(1,28) = 112.94$, $p < 0.001$] on μ .

Fig. 5.3: Comparison of peak grip force (PGF) for low μ and high μ subjects under dry and wet conditions for experimental and simulated (full training=F, partial training=P). Error bars represent the standard deviation. Published in (Gupta *et al.*, In press).

The change in PGF due to intrinsic variation and transient variation in μ is shown in Fig. 5.3. PGF is found to be lower for high intrinsic μ subjects when compared to the low μ subjects but this difference is statistically non-significant ($p=0.118$). PGF did not show significant changes due to dry/wet transition for low μ and high μ subjects, $p=0.784$ (Fig. 5.3). Using two way ANOVA a significant effect of intrinsic friction [$F(1,28) = 4.93, p < 0.05$] and a non-significant effect of dry-wet transition [$F(1,28) = 0.102, p = 0.75$] was observed on PGF.

Fig. 5.4: Comparison of stable grip force (SGF) for low μ and high μ subjects under dry and wet conditions for experimental and simulated (full training=F, partial training=P). Error bars represent the standard deviation. Published in (Gupta *et al.*, In press)

SGF is one of the key parameters in measuring the effect of μ on PGP. It is observed that low μ subjects generate a higher SGF than the high μ subjects but the change is statistically non-significant ($p=0.10$) (Fig. 5.4). During the dry - wet transition, a higher SGF was observed in wet case as compared to dry case ($p<0.01$). Two way ANOVA show a non-significant effect of intrinsic friction on the SGF [$F(1,28)=3.06, p=0.09$]. However, the dry-wet transition had a significant effect [$F(1,28)=9.52, p<0.005$] on SGF.

Fig. 5.5: Comparison of safety margin (SM) for low μ and high μ subjects under dry and wet conditions for experimental and simulated (full training=F, partial training=P). Error bars represent the standard deviation. Published in (Gupta *et al.*, In press)

The average safety margin ($SM = SGF - \text{slip force}$) did not show any significant change for intrinsic μ ($p=0.963$). Also, no significant effect of wetting the fingers (acute change in μ) was observed on SM ($p=0.875$) (Fig. 5.5). Using two way ANOVA a non-significant effect of intrinsic friction [$F(1,28) = 0.005$, $p=0.94$] and dry-wet transition [$F(1,28) = 1.42$, $p=0.24$] was observed on SM.

Fig. 5.6: Comparison of PGF/SGF ratio for low μ and high μ subjects under dry and wet conditions for experimental and simulated (full training=F, partial training=P). Error bars represent the standard deviation. Published in (Gupta *et al.*, In press)

The PGF/SGF ratio (Fig. 5.6) for intrinsic μ does not show any significant change ($p=0.915$). However, the transient (dry to wet) change in μ shows a significant decrease in PGF/SGF ratio ($p<0.01$). Two way ANOVA analysis suggests a non-significant effect of intrinsic friction [$F(1,28)=0.14, p=0.7$] and a significant effect of dry-wet transition [$F(1,28)=7.83, p<0.01$] on PGF/SGF ratio.

Fig. 5.7: Single trial study for wet condition for subject S3. The GF gradually builds up to a steady state value without showing a peak in the acute (PGF < SGF). Published in (Gupta *et al.*, In press)

It is interesting that some subjects generated a GF profile in which there was no sharp peak followed by a lesser SGF; F_G gradually increased and approached SGF instead. In dry conditions only one subject (S3) exhibited such an effect. Under dry wet conditions, such F_G profile (SGF > PGF) was seen for five subjects (S1, S3, S8, S9 and S16) (Fig. 5.7).

Table 1: Table showing the subject identification number (ID), PID_{KL} , $PID_{KG,dry}$, $PID_{KG,wet}$ (F) and $PID_{KG,wet}$ (P). Here (F) and (P) means fully trained values and partially trained values. Please note that for the $PID_{KG,dry}$, $PID_{KG,wet}$ (F) and $PID_{KG,wet}$ (P) the following parameters were kept constant $K_D=9$, $\tau_F=0.06$ and $\tau_E=0.8$. Published in (Gupta *et al.*, In press)

ID	PID_{KL}				$PID_{KG,dry}$		$PID_{KG,wet}$ (F)		$PID_{KG,wet}$ (P)	
	K_P	K_I	K_D	τ_F	K_P	K_I	K_P	K_I	K_P	K_I
S1	6.93	14.48	1.38	0.087	252.15	200.12	158.60	188.14	159.87	186.96
S2	6.90	14.48	1.37	0.093	491.37	410.77	322.19	295.56	302.97	307.71
S3	7.15	15.37	1.36	0.092	236.19	336.96	240.19	365.66	244.63	352.90
S4	7.36	14.48	1.46	0.092	478.75	323.39	276.24	210.80	271.36	214.30
S5	7.30	14.58	1.37	0.088	686.35	478.24	341.77	331.64	333.97	319.74
S6	7.14	14.71	1.46	0.092	783.01	336.04	328.71	188.65	341.88	175.95
S7	7.02	14.92	1.36	0.089	626.20	427.77	264.47	211.54	260.71	206.48
S8	7.22	14.66	1.46	0.092	600.50	655.09	308.58	417.76	302.75	434.96
S9	7.01	14.80	1.45	0.086	376.45	343.18	191.63	248.83	199.30	242.36
S10	6.93	15.49	1.40	0.092	697.98	413.57	326.61	257.79	346.68	247.25
S11	6.99	15.24	1.42	0.090	865.88	453.50	255.88	260.50	268.83	270.77
S12	6.94	14.70	1.47	0.088	584.35	430.22	274.35	250.22	280.40	258.55
S13	6.76	14.99	1.44	0.088	573.85	311.24	293.85	229.85	300.75	227.36
S14	6.92	14.61	1.47	0.088	529.54	409.91	252.49	232.90	256.78	243.42
S15	6.73	15.44	1.40	0.092	543.00	431.91	291.03	268.91	287.83	281.05
S16	7.16	15.29	1.43	0.087	678.20	460.48	192.01	235.00	181.70	242.91

5.5.2 Simulation results

Fig. 5.8: Figure showing the average distance between individuals with number of generations for GA for subject S2 under dry and wet condition (with and without noise).

We present a computational model that can be used to explain the PGF and SGF values from the experimental data. The simulation parameters (PID_{KL} , $PID_{KG,dry}$ and $PID_{KG,wet}$) were trained using GA (GA convergence is shown in Fig. 5.8 and Fig. 5.9). For a detailed list of PID parameters refer Table 1. Two methods of training were employed for $PID_{KG,wet}$. Following the intuitive idea that not much time is available

for retraining in the wet case, we train the PID parameters 1) fully (until convergence) and 2) partially (stop training before convergence) in the wet condition. In the second method which involves partial training, we train $PID_{KG,wet}$ for a small number (=5) of generations compared to the higher (>50) number of generations used in the corresponding dry condition. PID_{KL} parameters are directly borrowed from the dry condition and used in wet condition.

Fig. 5.9: Figure showing the mean fitness of individuals with number of generations for GA for subject S2 under dry and wet condition (with and without noise).

In the first method which involved full training (trained for >50 generations) of the $PID_{KG,wet}$ parameters, it was observed that very low average percentage error (APE) when compared to the experimental wet condition were obtained (APE \pm SD is 0.32 ± 0.16 for PGF and 0.31 ± 0.22 for SGF) with range [0.02 0.76]. In particular, in case of low μ subjects, simulation obtained APE \pm SD for PGF as 0.38 ± 0.16 and SGF as 0.34 ± 0.27 . This error is slightly lesser for high μ subjects with APE \pm SD for PGF as 0.28 ± 0.14 and SGF as 0.29 ± 0.17 .

The second method (table 2 and table 3) of training in which partial training was imparted shows considerably higher APE \pm SD (2.3 ± 1.33 for PGF and 3.40 ± 1.50 for SGF) with higher range [0.02 6.21] for simulated data. The low μ subject's data had APE \pm SD for PGF as 1.98 ± 1.08 and SGF as 3.19 ± 1.81 whereas for high μ subject's simulated data APE \pm SD obtained was 2.55 ± 1.45 and 1.57 ± 1.18 for PGF and SGF respectively.

Table 2: Table showing the subject identification number (ID), age, subject type (High /low friction), coefficient of friction for dry case (μ_d) and the corresponding peak grip force (PGF) and steady state grip force (SGF) for both experiment and simulation (full training) for dry skin friction condition. All Values of PGF and SGF are in Newton. Published in (Gupta *et al.*, In press)

ID	Type	Age (yrs)	Experimental			Simulation (full training)		Simulation % Error	
			μ_d	PGF	SGF	PGF	SGF	PGF	SGF
S1	Low	30	0.41 ± 0.04	2.91 ± 0.53	2.07 ± 0.24	2.9	2.08	0.12	0.54
S2	Low	52	0.59 ± 0.20	3.66 ± 0.48	2.73 ± 0.35	3.66	2.73	0.03	0.02
S3	Low	26	0.60 ± 0.07	2.29 ± 0.24	2.66 ± 0.23	2.29	2.67	0.14	0.31
S4	Low	33	0.65 ± 0.06	3.38 ± 0.86	2.10 ± 0.32	3.38	2.1	0.07	0.33
S5	Low	32	0.74 ± 0.08	3.85 ± 0.46	2.45 ± 0.18	3.84	2.44	0.26	0.29
S6	Low	37	0.75 ± 0.11	4.18 ± 0.49	1.72 ± 0.19	4.15	1.71	0.57	0.57
S7	Low	46	0.76 ± 0.06	3.49 ± 0.40	2.18 ± 0.27	3.48	2.17	0.23	0.33
S8	High	39	0.88 ± 0.15	3.42 ± 0.38	3.17 ± 0.61	3.4	3.18	0.41	0.21
S9	High	33	0.89 ± 0.14	2.11 ± 0.31	1.70 ± 0.30	2.1	1.69	0.2	0.22
S10	High	53	0.93 ± 0.07	3.58 ± 0.74	1.97 ± 0.45	3.57	1.97	0.11	0.01
S11	High	32	0.94 ± 0.22	3.55 ± 0.48	1.74 ± 0.08	3.55	1.75	0.03	0.71
S12	High	46	0.95 ± 0.09	3.06 ± 0.42	2.04 ± 0.19	3.06	2.04	0.15	0.1
S13	High	29	0.97 ± 0.08	2.91 ± 0.32	1.47 ± 0.30	2.9	1.48	0.35	0.39
S14	High	28	1.02 ± 0.11	2.24 ± 0.53	1.56 ± 0.30	2.24	1.57	0.35	0.47
S15	High	33	1.05 ± 0.09	2.31 ± 0.16	1.64 ± 0.19	2.29	1.64	0.7	0.17
S16	High	26	1.07 ± 0.09	2.77 ± 0.40	1.72 ± 0.19	2.77	1.73	0.08	0.25

Table 3: Table showing the subject identification number (ID), age, type (High /low friction), coefficient of friction (μ) and the corresponding peak grip force (PGF) and steady state grip force (SGF) for both experiment and the simulation (with full training) for wet skin friction condition. All Values of PGF and SGF are in Newton. Published in (Gupta *et al.*, In press)

	Experimental			Simulation		Simulation	
				(full training)		% Error	
ID	μ_w	PGF	SGF	PGF	SGF	PGF	SGF
S1	0.32 ± 0.02	2.78 ± 0.33	2.82 ± 0.49	2.77	2.81	0.31	0.21
S2	0.43 ± 0.10	3.71 ± 0.37	3.00 ± 0.30	3.73	3.02	0.53	0.68
S3	0.53 ± 0.02	2.45 ± 0.59	3.02 ± 0.73	2.46	3.01	0.38	0.06
S4	0.32 ± 0.04	3.97 ± 0.42	2.74 ± 0.34	3.95	2.74	0.42	0.06
S5	0.46 ± 0.06	3.33 ± 0.76	2.83 ± 0.46	3.33	2.83	0.02	0.15
S6	0.47 ± 0.04	3.01 ± 0.12	1.61 ± 0.15	3	1.62	0.47	0.47
S7	0.36 ± 0.03	3.68 ± 0.41	2.62 ± 0.10	3.66	2.64	0.51	0.76
S8	0.61 ± 0.04	2.49 ± 0.32	2.76 ± 0.11	2.48	2.77	0.44	0.39
S9	0.33 ± 0.03	2.93 ± 0.47	3.19 ± 0.26	2.95	3.2	0.53	0.28
S10	0.37 ± 0.03	3.88 ± 1.07	2.75 ± 0.43	3.88	2.76	0.19	0.22
S11	0.63 ± 0.08	1.95 ± 0.29	1.71 ± 0.37	1.94	1.72	0.32	0.71
S12	0.46 ± 0.06	3.11 ± 0.40	2.51 ± 0.22	3.12	2.51	0.06	0.07
S13	0.39 ± 0.05	3.43 ± 0.70	2.41 ± 0.36	3.42	2.42	0.11	0.25
S14	0.43 ± 0.01	2.95 ± 0.39	2.39 ± 0.23	2.94	2.4	0.34	0.14
S15	0.55 ± 0.05	2.67 ± 0.44	2.19 ± 0.32	2.68	2.18	0.25	0.22
S16	0.40 ± 0.03	2.38 ± 0.26	2.47 ± 0.21	2.39	2.48	0.25	0.3

Fig. 5.10: Figure illustrating the change in K_p , K_i , K_d and $\tau_{F,L}$ for PID_{KL} and change in cost function (C_L); mean object position (\bar{X}_o); peak object position max (X_o); and variance in object position (σ_x). Each bar represents the mean \pm SD for subjects S1 and S16.

Fig. 5.11: Figure illustrating the change in K_P , K_I , (keeping K_D , $\tau_{E,G}$ and $\tau_{F,G}$ constant) for $PID_{K_G,dry}$ and cost function for F_G controller (C_G), peak FG (PGF), steady state FG (SGF) and slip distance (distance between the finger and object position). Each bar represents the mean \pm SD for subjects S1 and S16.

Fig. 5.12: Figure illustrating the change in K_p , K_i , (keeping K_D , $\tau_{E,G}$ and $\tau_{F,G}$ constant) for $PID_{K_G,wet}$ and cost function for F_G controller (C_G), peak F_G (PGF), steady state F_G (SGF) and slip distance (distance between the finger and object position). Each bar represents the mean \pm SD for subjects S1 and S16.

The model was cross validated by simulating the GA 10 times for each subject to obtain optimal PID_{K_L} and PID_{K_G} values. These PID values were then used to calculate the model outputs [cost function for F_L controller (C_L), mean object position (\bar{X}_o), peak object position $\max(X_o)$, and variance in object position (σ_X) for PID_{K_L} ; cost function for F_G controller (C_G), peak F_G (PGF), steady state F_G (SGF) and slip distance (distance between the finger and object position) for $PID_{K_G,dry}$ and $PID_{K_G,wet}$].

The mean \pm SD of input parameters and model outputs was computed and plotted for subjects S1 and S16 (refer Fig. 5.10, Fig. 5.11 and Fig. 5.12).

Table 4: Table showing the subject identification number (ID), coefficient of friction (μ_w) and the peak grip force (PGF) and steady state grip force (SGF) for experimental data and simulated data when using $PID_{KG,dry}$ and μ_w ($PID_{KG,dry} + \mu_w$) and partially training $PID_{KG,wet}$. All Values of PGF and SGF are in Newton. Published in (Gupta *et al.*, In press)

ID	μ_w	Experimental		Simulation ($PID_{KG,dry} + \mu_w$)		Percentage error ($PID_{KG,dry} + \mu_w$)		Simulation (for partially trained $PID_{KG,wet}$)		Percentage error (for partially trained $PID_{KG,wet}$)	
		PGF	SGF	PGF	SGF	PGF	SGF	PGF	SGF	PGF	SGF
S1	0.32	2.78	2.82	3	2.36	7.91	16.31	2.79	2.79	0.23	0.84
S2	0.43	3.71	3	3.63	3.18	2.16	6	3.57	3.15	3.91	4.9
S3	0.53	2.45	3.02	2.3	2.77	6.12	8.28	2.47	2.91	1.05	3.55
S4	0.32	3.97	2.74	3.65	2.95	8.06	7.66	3.9	2.78	1.73	1.6
S5	0.46	3.33	2.83	4.59	2.92	37.84	3.18	3.25	2.73	2.44	3.66
S6	0.47	3.01	1.61	4.18	2.04	38.87	26.71	3.09	1.51	2.45	6.21
S7	0.36	3.68	2.62	3.49	2.95	5.16	12.6	3.6	2.58	2.03	1.59
S8	0.61	2.49	2.76	7.66	7.12	207.63	157.97	2.46	2.88	1.12	4.52
S9	0.33	2.93	3.19	3.87	3.07	32.08	3.76	3.02	3.11	3.25	2.35
S10	0.37	3.88	2.75	5.16	2.84	32.99	3.27	4.06	2.64	4.55	3.91
S11	0.63	1.95	1.71	3.68	1.8	88.72	5.26	2.04	1.79	4.53	4.6
S12	0.46	3.11	2.51	5	3.34	60.77	33.07	3.19	2.6	2.41	3.32
S13	0.39	3.43	2.41	3.63	2.12	5.83	12.03	3.49	2.39	1.78	0.85
S14	0.43	2.95	2.39	3.19	2.35	8.14	1.67	3	2.5	1.75	4.59
S15	0.55	2.67	2.19	2.31	2.2	13.48	0.46	2.67	2.28	0.02	4.26
S16	0.4	2.38	2.47	3.82	2.37	60.05	4.09	2.3	2.56	3.53	3.7

Interestingly, if only μ was changed from dry (μ_d) to wet (μ_w), and all the PID parameters are straight away borrowed from dry condition to wet condition, APE \pm

SD obtained for PGF was 38.49 ± 50.07 and for SGF was 18.90 ± 36.97 (Table 4). These errors are very high because of the high range of the percentage errors [0.46 207.63]. It was also observed that lower APE \pm SD was observed for the low friction subjects for PGF (15.16 ± 14.78) and SGF (11.53 ± 7.37) when compared to the high friction subjects PGF (56.63 ± 59.46) and SGF (24.62 ± 48.09), respectively. Actually half of the subjects show percentage error in PGF $< 10\%$, and 10 (out of 16) subjects show SGF $< 10\%$. These results strongly suggest that the model trained under dry conditions can contribute significantly to the model under wet conditions. Therefore, when $PID_{KG,dry}$ is used to initialize PID_{KG} in wet conditions, and partially trained with the altered friction μ_w , (PID_{KL} is the same i.e., $PID_{KL,dry} = PID_{KL,wet}$) accuracy improved dramatically. Further improvement in accuracy was observed when is $PID_{KG,wet}$ is fully trained.

Since the simulated data obtained were very close to the experimental data, no significant differences in the ANOVA results were obtained between simulation and experiment. Simulated results also show the intrinsic PGF to be lower for high μ subjects when compared to the low μ subjects. The two way ANOVA suggests that a significant effect of intrinsic friction [$F(1,28) = 4.93, p = 0.035$] and a non-significant effect of dry wet transition [$F(1,28) = 0.095, p = 0.76$] on PGF.

The simulated SGF shows that low μ subjects generate a higher SGF than the high μ subjects. It is observed that during dry - wet transition, a higher SGF was observed in

wet case as compared to dry case. Two way ANOVA shows a non-significant effect of intrinsic friction [$F(1,28) = 2.986$, $p = 0.095$] and a significant effect of dry-wet transition [$F(1,28) = 9.661$] on SGF.

The simulated result for average safety margin show SM to be constant for both the dry and wet condition for both high and low μ subjects. Two way ANOVA suggest a non-significant effect of intrinsic friction [$F(1,28) = 0.003$, $p = 0.958$] and dry-wet transition [$F(1,28) = 1.35$, $p = 0.255$] on SM.

Simulated PGF/SGF ratio is lower in high μ subjects than in low μ subjects. During wetting it is observed that this ratio decreases. Using two way ANOVA, a non-significant effect of intrinsic friction [$F(1,28) = 0.162$, $p = 0.69$] and significant effect of dry-wet transition [$F(1,28) = 8.00$, $p = 0.009$] on the PGF/SGF ratio was obtained.

5.6 DISCUSSION

In the present study we investigated the role of skin friction changes due to: 1) intrinsic friction, and 2) acute friction change by wetting, on PG performance. The study involves both experimental and simulation components. Four different metrics related to PG performance are considered: PGF, SGF, safety margin and PGF/SGF ratio. Variations in these four metrics to due to acute changes in friction and intrinsic friction are reported.

5.6.1 Experimental task

It was previously reported that moderate skin hydration reduces the μ but a further increase in the hydration levels increases μ (Zackrisson *et al.*, 2008; Andre *et al.*, 2010). However, in the current study we found that on wetting the fingers (involved in gripping the object), in all the cases, μ decreased. This might be due to water forming a continuous layer which acts as a lubricant, thereby reducing friction. In our experiments, the hydration levels were not sufficiently high to show an increase in μ . It was observed that subjects with high intrinsic friction show a greater decrease in μ during dry-wet transition, than in case of low intrinsic friction group. This tendency may be attributed to the absolute limit of friction for Plexiglas and finger surface ($\mu_{\text{abs}} \approx 0.4$ to 0.55) with water as lubricant.

High PGF prevents the object from slipping during the initial lifting process. A non-significant difference was observed in PGF change from dry to wet conditions (for both high and low friction groups). In the current scenario, it is possible that an estimate of desired F_G from the dry condition is used for the wet condition. But if an inadequate PGF is generated, this information is conveyed by the feedback which arrives after a delay. The feedback causes a further increase in F_G , resulting in higher PGF. There was a significant difference in PGF between high μ subjects and low μ which suggests that PGF is dependent on the intrinsic μ . Thus, we may summarize

that PGF change due to acute (dry/wet) change in friction is object dependent, while PGF change due to intrinsic friction is individual dependent.

In general the SGF generated is higher for a low friction case than for a high friction case. SGF shows a significant change in the dry-wet transition if we lump the high and low μ subjects together. Though we observe that SGF is higher in low μ subjects compared to high μ subjects in dry conditions, the corresponding difference in wet conditions was insignificant. This observation that SGF does not show much variation between low μ subjects compared to high μ subjects under wet conditions, may perhaps have its roots in the fact that SGF, unlike PGF, is more influenced by the current friction value, which is more narrowly distributed under wet conditions. These results are in general accordance with the existing literature suggesting increase of SGF for decreasing μ (Johansson *et al.*, 1984; Westling *et al.*, 1984b; Johansson *et al.*, 1988a; Forssberg *et al.*, 1991b; Gordon *et al.*, 1991; Forssberg *et al.*, 1995; Johansson, 1999; Saels *et al.*, 1999; Zhang *et al.*, 1999; Andre *et al.*, 2009).

The average value of SM was maintained in a very narrow band for all the four categories of interest: low and high μ subjects and for dry/wet conditions. The result suggests that SM is more dependent on the object rather than the friction or the individual.

The average PGF/SGF ratio is nearly the same for both low μ subjects and high μ subjects under the dry condition, whereas the ratio is lower for high μ subjects than for low μ subjects under wet conditions. A natural explanation to this trend is the fact that PGF is nearly the same between dry and wet conditions, while SGF is higher in wet conditions.

In some grip profiles, F_G has no peak; F_G rises gradually to a steady state value (Fig. 5.7). This type of F_G profile was not reported previously. Only one subject in the dry case generated the “SGF > PGF” type of profile and five subjects in wet case showed this type of profile. It is possible that the subjects employ one of two strategies (PGF > SGF and PGF < SGF) for F_G generation and a low friction condition favors selection of SGF > PGF profile. We pointed out earlier that the change in PGF due to dry/wet transition is not significant. This is probably because the PGF is determined by the prior experience with the object, whereas SGF is determined in real-time by feedback related to object slippage. If the initial estimate of the required F_G is high, the F_G profile visits a peak value and then comes to a stable value (Fig. 2.3). On the other hand, if the initial estimates are too low, the F_G will continue to build up beyond the initial estimate, creating a profile in which there is no peak.

Table 5: Summary of changes in PGF, SGF, SM and PGF/SGF due to intrinsic (High μ Vs low μ) and acute (Dry case Vs wet case) changes in μ . SD represents significant difference and ND represent non-significant difference.

	High μ Vs low μ	Dry case Vs wet case
PGF	SD	ND
SGF	ND	SD
SM	ND	ND
PGF/SGF	ND	SD

Table 5 presents a summary of PGF, SGF, SM and PGF/SGF due to intrinsic (high μ Vs low μ) and acute (dry case Vs wet case) changes in μ .

5.6.2 Computational model

The proposed computational model generates very accurate results with errors $<1\%$ for both dry and wet cases for all the 16 subjects when full training was provided. However, higher error was observed in partial training of $PID_{KG,wet}$. In all the cases of partial training, the safety margin prevents the object from slipping. The partial training helps the subjects to rapidly adapt to the change in μ . This explains how the rapid training enables successful lift when the μ reduces drastically. The normal dry condition controller parameters may be trained over many encounters with different objects but under suddenly reduced μ the controller parameters for dry case may be used as an initial for controller training.

A revealing feature of the model is that PID_{KL} is the same for both dry and wet conditions, whereas PID_{KG} is retrained (both partially and fully) for wet conditions. The fact that the same controller for F_L works well for both dry and wet conditions, while the F_G controller needs to be retrained, suggests that the neural substrates for lifting and PG are probably different. fMRI-based studies on neural substrates of PG performance shed some light on this point (Ehrsson *et al.*, 2001; Ehrsson *et al.*, 2003). Ehrsson *et al.* (2001) found preferential activation of bilateral cortex lining the inferior part of the precentral sulcus, the rostral cingulate motor area, and the right intraparietal cortex when the subjects were engaged in PG tasks. A subsequent study Ehrsson *et al.* (2003), considered three tasks related to PG generation: 1) the grip-load force task in which the subjects both grip and lift the object, 2) the F_G task in which the subjects only grip the object without lifting it, and 3) the load force task in which the subjects lift the object, without gripping it, by pressing upwards against a horizontal yoke fixed to the top of the object. When activation produced during the grip-load force task was compared with that of F_G alone, there was preferential activation of a part of posterior intraparietal sulcus (IPS). However, when activation produced during the grip-load force task was compared with that of load force alone, there was activation in right prefrontal area, in addition to the same part of posterior IPS activated in the previous case. These results indicate that it is possible to double-dissociate the respective substrates of lifting and gripping in PG performance (Ehrsson *et al.*, 2001; Ehrsson *et al.*, 2003).

The same concept may be applied to the fact that when encountering novel objects the information about the previous encounters with the same or similar objects serve as the initial template for the parameter optimization (Gordon *et al.*, 1993).

Till now we discussed how the intrinsic friction and acute change (brought about by wetting) can affect the precision grip force performance. Now in the following chapter we will discuss how the optimal grip force is selected for a task and how does the optimal GF vary in controls and PD condition.

CHAPTER 6

A UTILITY BASED MODEL FOR PRECISION GRIP PERFORMANCE IN PARKINSON'S DISEASE PATIENTS.

6.1 INTRODUCTION

As described in Chapter 2, an excessive GF can damage the object being manipulated and fatigue the muscles; and a low GF might prevent the task from reaching completion. Hence, there is a GF range operating within which the task can be completed without causing fatigue. The subject might generate GF values which are either towards the extremes of the range or mid-ranged. What causes the subject to choose either extreme values or mid-range values forms the motivation for the present study. We also aim to develop a computational model for precision grip force generation for healthy controls and then simulate the effect of reduced dopamine levels (to represent PD condition) on PG performance.

A critical feature of the PG performance is the safety margin (SM). SM, which is defined as $(SGF - F_{crit})$, determines robustness of PG lift against perturbations in load. Using a small SM might increase the number of failures with number of trials. A small SM may make the gripping unstable; therefore, in order to minimize risk one must operate sufficiently far from the edge of instability. Due to generation of large SM it is evident that concepts from theories of risk-dependent decision making (DM)

may be applied to understand PG performance (Bell, 1995; d'Acremont *et al.*, 2009). In the risk-based decision making, risk is defined as variance in reward outcome (Bell, 1995; d'Acremont *et al.*, 2009). In the context of PG performance, successful lift may be thought to be associated with a reward. The two terms that are critical for expected utility are mean and variance (Levy *et al.*, 1979). Similarly, in the PG task the expected reward (value) mean saturates for GF levels that are much greater than F_{crit} . The variance in the expected reward (risk) is highest close to F_{crit} . An optimal PG consists of maximizing mean reward (value) while minimizing the variance (risk). The present study approaches the problem of PG performance in terms of risk minimization strategy and describes it within the framework of RL. The model is used to explain PG performance in both controls and PD patients.

PG studies in PD patients show a remarkable difference in SM generated between PD patients and controls (Ingvarsson *et al.*, 1997; Fellows *et al.*, 1998). These differences can be a result of memory impairment or sensory deficit or altered decision making. Interestingly, PD patients are capable of storing and recalling previous lift parameters (Muller *et al.*, 1990; Ehrsson *et al.*, 2003), which enables them to scale GF when the load force on the object changes (Gordon *et al.*, 1997; Fellows *et al.*, 1998). Hence the role of memory in altered PD can be ruled out. Sensory deficit can (Westling *et al.*, 1984a; Nowak *et al.*, 2001; Fisher *et al.*, 2002; Monzée *et al.*, 2003) affect the precision grip performance. But whether these sensory deficits are a cause of altered SM in PD is a matter of debate. A school of thought considers the sensory deficit as

the cause of altered SM in PD (Moore, 1987; Schneider *et al.*, 1987; Klockgether *et al.*, 1995; Jobst *et al.*, 1997; Nolano *et al.*, 2008), which is opposed by others (Gordon *et al.*, 1997; Ingvarsson *et al.*, 1997). The controls and PD OFF subjects generate nearly similar SGFs whereas a higher SM was generated under the medicated state for silk surface (Ingvarsson *et al.*, 1997). This increase in SGF is due to the L-Dopa induced hyperkinesias (Ingvarsson *et al.*, 1997; Gordon *et al.*, 1999). Another study (Fellows *et al.*, 1998), which only considered the PD ON and controls, observed that PD ON subjects show a higher SGF than controls (Fellows *et al.*, 1998). The SGF variance is also considerably higher in PD OFF condition when compared to controls and PD ON condition (Ingvarsson *et al.*, 1997). Therefore, the concepts of risk sensitivity can be applied to understand the SGF in controls, PD ON and PD OFF conditions.

Recently it was discovered that the risk-takers are less prone to PD (Sullivan *et al.*, 2012) and PD medications such as L-Dopa (Ehrsson *et al.*, 2003) and dopamine agonists (Claassen *et al.*, 2011) increase impulsivity and risk-seeking behavior in PD patients. PD subjects under medication tend to show less sensitivity to negative outcomes and therefore tend to make risky choices (Lawrence *et al.*, 2003; Claassen *et al.*, 2011). The effect of PD medication (dopamine agonist) in enhancing risk-seeking tendency was also confirmed using the Balloon Analogue Risk Task—an elegant assay for risk-related behavior (Claassen *et al.*, 2011). It is also known that the sensorimotor control can be treated as a risk sensitivity problem (Braun *et al.*, 2011).

The impairment of risk-processing in PD patients (Lawrence *et al.*, 2003; Frank *et al.*, 2004a; Witt, 2007; Claassen *et al.*, 2011), and altered SM in PD, makes a risk-based motor control approach to PG performance even more compelling.

None of the previously explained computational models for PG lift tasks (Kim *et al.*, 1994; Fagergren *et al.*, 2003; de Gruijl *et al.*, 2009) explain the FG levels used by controls and PD patients. Hence, a computational model to explain FGs in controls and PD forms the motivation for the present work.

In the present model, we use the concept of utility function, a combination of value and risk components, embedded in the framework of Reinforcement Learning (RL) (Bell, 1995; Long *et al.*, 2009; Wu *et al.*, 2009; Braun *et al.*, 2011; Wolpert *et al.*, 2012). Concepts from RL have been used extensively in the past to model the function of the Basal Ganglia (BG) in control and PD conditions (Sridharan *et al.*, 2006; Gangadhar *et al.*, 2008; Gangadhar *et al.*, 2009; Chakravarthy *et al.*, 2010; Krishnan *et al.*, 2011; Magdoom *et al.*, 2011; Kalva *et al.*, 2012; Pragathi Priyadharsini *et al.*, 2012; Sukumar *et al.*, 2012). Recently, through utility function formulation, the role of the BG in reward, punishment and risk based learning (Pragathi Priyadharsini *et al.*, 2012) was modeled.

In the following sections we will present a computational model for human PG performance in controls and PD subjects in (ON/OFF) medicated states. Using risk-

based DM to model PG performance, we show the alteration of F_G in PD patients (Wolpert *et al.*, 2012) in a modified RL framework. Modeling results match favorably with experimental PG performance.

6.2 MODEL

6.2.1 The complete proposed PG model in a nutshell

- The first step is to define a closed-loop control system in which the plant (the finger and object system) is controlled by two controllers (F_L controller and F_G). The system receives two inputs reference F_G (F_{Gref}) and a reference position (X_{ref}). The reference position, the position to which the object must be lifted, is constant for a task and is specified by the experimenter. The other input to the system, the reference grip force F_{Gref} , is a crucial parameter that determines the PG performance of the control system. The F_{Gref} is the step input to the F_G controller and the output of the controller, $F_G(T)$, is used to grip the object ('T' denotes simulation time in *milliseconds*). The challenge consists of finding F_{Gref} that leads to successful lifts.
- The next step is Utility function, $U(F_{Gref})$, formulation which consists of both value and risk components which are in turn functions of F_{Gref} . The problem of finding the optimal F_{Gref} is then treated as an action selection problem in the BG. In previous studies, the Go-Explore-NoGo (GEN) (Magdoom *et al.*, 2011; Sukumar *et al.*, 2012) model is used as a model of action selection in the BG. In the present study, we apply GEN on $U(F_{Gref})$ to simulate PG performance results for control and PD condition.
- Using the gradient of the Utility function, δ_U (representing the dopamine signal), as a key signal in control of action selection, we simulate the PG performances of controls and PD subjects in the experimental tasks by Fellows *et al.* (1998) and Ingvarsson *et al.* (1997).

6.2.2 The PG Control System

Fig. 6.1: (a) A free body diagram showing the forces acting on object and finger. F_G , F_L , F_f , F_n stands for Grip, Lift, frictional and normal forces, respectively. (b) The figure showing the coupling between the finger and the object. Published in (Gupta *et al.*, 2013)

A precision grip-lift task comprises of gripping the object in the two finger grip (formed by index finger and thumb). The hand and object interact through friction (coefficient of friction is represented as μ) between the fingers and the object. A free

body diagram showing the various forces acting on the fingers and the object are shown in Fig. 6.1. The fingers, shown in two parts on either side of the object, represent the index finger and the thumb. For simplicity we assume that the two fingers are identical in mass and shape.

F_G is the grip force applied on the object horizontally acting in opposite directions. F_L is the lift force acting at the finger-object interface, lifting the object up. By the action of the F_G pressing on the object, and due to the friction between the finger and object, F_L gets coupled to the object. The forces thus emerging between the finger and object are shown in Fig. 6.1 (b). The frictional force F_f acts on the object in the upward direction, with $F_f/2$ on either side of the object.

Fig. 6.2: Block diagram showing (a) the interaction of the various components and their corresponding inputs and outputs. X , \dot{X} and \ddot{X} are the position, velocity and acceleration; subscript 'fin' and 'o' denote finger and object respectively; (b) the control loop used for F_L controller design. The F_G in the full system of (a) is set to a constant value of 10N. Published in (Gupta *et al.*, 2013).

Fig. 6.2 (a) illustrates the interaction of F_L and F_G in controlling the position of the object (X_o). The model consists of two controllers (F_L and F_G controllers) and a plant. Inputs to the plant are F_L and F_G while the outputs are the object position (X_o), finger position (X_{fin}) and their derivatives (\dot{X}_o , \ddot{X}_o , \dot{X}_{fin} , \ddot{X}_{fin}). The objective of the control task is to lift the object to a reference position, X_{ref} . The model receives F_{Gref} and X_{ref} as the inputs and the X_{fin} (position of finger), X_o (position of object), \dot{X}_{fin} (velocity of finger), \dot{X}_o (velocity of object), \ddot{X}_{fin} (acceleration of finger) and \ddot{X}_o (acceleration of object) as outputs.

The following sections describe the design of the controllers (F_G and F_L) and plant followed by their training method.

6.2.3 The Grip force (F_G) controller

In the current study, the F_G controller is considered as a second order system to generate the F_G which couples the fingers to the object. A typical F_G profile of human subjects shows a peak and a return to a steady state value, resembling the step-response of an underdamped second order system, thereby justifying the choice of an underdamped second order system as a minimal model. The F_G controller for a step input (F_{Gref}) is given in eqn.(6.1).

$$F_G = \frac{\omega_n^2}{(s^2 + 2 \omega_n \zeta s + \omega_n^2)} \quad (6.1)$$

In order to determine the values of natural frequency, ω_n and damping factor, ζ , maximum overshoot (M_p , defined as the maximum peak value of the response curve) and time to peak (T_p , peaking time of the response curve) are required. Using prior published experimental values (Johansson *et al.*, 1984) for M_p and T_p , F_G controller parameters are obtained using eqn. (6.2)-(6.3) (Ogata, 2002).

$$M_p = e^{-(\zeta \omega_n / \omega_d) \pi} \quad (6.2)$$

$$T_p = \frac{\pi}{\omega_d} \quad (6.3)$$

where, ω_d the damped natural frequency is given as,

$$\omega_d = \omega_n \sqrt{1 - \zeta^2} \quad (6.4)$$

6.2.4 Lift Force controller

The F_L controller, which is a PID controller (Eqn. (6.5)), takes the position error (E_L) as input (eqn. (6.6)), and produces a time-varying F_L profile ($F_{L,PID}$) as output (eqn. (6.5)) which in turn controls the object position.

$$F_{L,PID} = K_{P,L}E_L + K_{I,L} \int_0^T E_L(\tau_n) d\tau_n + K_{D,L} \frac{dE_L}{dT} \quad (6.5)$$

$$E_L = X_o - X_{ref} \quad (6.6)$$

Here the $K_{P,L}$, $K_{I,L}$ and $K_{D,L}$ are the proportional, integral and derivative gains, respectively for the F_L controller.

PID controller output is non-zero initially which is not realistic since the initial value of F_L must be zero. Hence, $F_{L,PID}$ is smoothened using eqn. (6.7).

$$\tau_s \frac{dF_L}{dT} = -F_L + F_{L,PID} \quad (6.7)$$

where, $F_L(T=0) = 0$.

6.2.5 Plant

The forces (F_L and F_G) obtained from the two controllers are used for determining the kinetic parameters (position, velocity and acceleration of finger and object). The net force acting on finger and object is given in eqn.(6.8) and eqn.(6.9). Please note that M_{fin} is kept constant at $M_{fin} = M_o/10$ in the model.

$$F_{fin} = F_L - F_f - M_{fin}g \quad (6.8)$$

$$F_o = F_f + F_n - M_o g \quad (6.9)$$

When the object is resting on surface the net force on object is zero as there is no acceleration. So, the normal force is obtained by keeping $F_o=0$ in eqn.(6.9). When the object is lifted from the table the normal force becomes zero. F_n determination is given in eqn.(6.10).

$$F_n = \begin{cases} M_o g - F_f, & \text{if } X_o = 0 \wedge M_o g > F_f \\ 0, & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (6.10)$$

The frictional force (F_f) coupling the finger and object is given in Eqn. (6.11)

$$F_f = \begin{cases} F_{noslip}, & \text{if } F_{noslip} < F_{slip} \\ F_{slip}, & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (6.11)$$

where, the F_{slip} , representing the maximum frictional force that can be generated is given in eqn.(6.12).

$$F_{slip} = 2\mu F_G \quad (6.12)$$

The F_f required to prevent slip is given in eqn. (6.13)

$$F_{noslip} = \frac{M_o M_{fin}}{M_o + M_{fin}} \left(\frac{F_L}{M_{fin}} - \frac{F_n}{M_o} \right) \quad (6.13)$$

Invoking Newton's second law, eqn.(6.8) and eqn.(6.9) can also be represented as eqn. (6.14)and eqn. (6.15).

$$F_{fin} = M_{fin} \frac{d^2 X_{fin}}{dx^2} \quad (6.14)$$

$$F_o = M_o \frac{d^2 X_o}{dt^2} \quad (6.15)$$

The kinetic parameters can be obtained by integrating $\frac{d^2 X_o}{dt^2}$ to obtain velocity and double integrated to obtain the position.

In order to design the F_L controller, we simplify the full system of Fig. 6.2 (a) as a F_L controller with a high constant F_G (10 N) to prevent the slip (Fig. 6.2 (b)). Note that if a constant and high value of F_G is assumed, slip is completely prevented, and the F_G controller is effectively eliminated from the complete system (Fig. 6.2 (b)). The F_L controller design now involves lifting a simple inertial load straight up from an initial position ($X_o=0m$) to a final position ($X_o=0.05m$).

Performance of the lift is evaluated using the cost function, CE, (eqn. (6.16)).This Cost function comprises of 1) average position difference between the finger (\bar{X}_{fin})

and the object (\bar{X}_o) at the end of the trial and 2) the difference in position between the desired and actual average position of the object.

$$CE (F_{Gref}) = 0.5 \left(\frac{\bar{X}_{fin} - \bar{X}_o}{\bar{X}_{fin}} \right)^2 + 0.5 \left(\frac{X_{ref} - \bar{X}_o}{X_{ref}} \right)^2 \quad (6.16)$$

The F_L PID controller parameters were then optimized for cost function (CE) using GA (Goldberg, 1989; Whitley, 1994) (refer Fig. 6.3 for block diagram and for parameters refer Table 6) keeping F_G constant (=10 N) at a sufficiently high value so that the object does not slip.

Table 6: The Genetic Algorithm (Goldberg, 1989) option set for optimization is given in the adjoining table. Optimization toolbox 6.0, MatlabR2011a, Mathworks Inc. is used. Here, CE= cost function to evaluate the performance of lift (eqn.(6.16)). Published in (Gupta *et al.*, 2013).

Option	Option set for determining FL controller parameters
Population Size	100
Crossover fraction	0.8
Elite count	4
Generation time	1000
Function tolerance	1 e-6
Cost function	CE

The F_L controller described above is designed assuming a constant and high F_G . But, when both F_G and F_L controllers are inserted in the full system (Fig. 6.2 (a)), the

system may behave in a very different manner due to gradual F_G buildup starting from zero. When a step input of magnitude F_{Gref} is given to the F_G controller, the F_G starts from 0, then approaches a peak value and stabilizes at a steady-state value known as SGF. Even with the trained controllers, for low values of F_{Gref} , the object may slip. But once the F_{Gref} is sufficiently high, slip is prevented and the object can be lifted successfully. Therefore, for a successful lift, an optimal value of F_{Gref} needs to be determined. The optimal F_{Gref} , which is related to SGF needed for a successful grip/lift performance, varies with the experimental setup, skin friction etc. (Ingvarsson *et al.*, 1997; Fellows *et al.*, 1998). It is here that we use concepts from RL and the utility function formulation for searching the F_{Gref} state space.

Fig. 6.3: Block diagram showing the training mechanism of the F_L controller. Published in (Gupta *et al.*, 2013).

6.2.6 The Utility function formulation:

The optimality of a decision is measured by the rewards fetched by it. Selection of an optimal choice providing the maximum expected value of the rewards (value) is known as optimal decision making (DM). DM can be seen in stock exchange, corporates and even our daily lives (which may or may not involve explicit monetary rewards). A lot of DM is carried out subconsciously when the person is unaware of the reason for making a decision (Ferber *et al.*, 1967). Non-human primates also show DM capabilities (Lakshminarayanan *et al.*, 2011; Leathers *et al.*, 2012). A mathematical framework is essential to empirically understand subjective DM behavior. Various independent studies confirm the role of value (average reward) and risk (variance in the rewards) in DM (Milton *et al.*, 1948; Markowitz, 1952; Hanoch *et al.*, 1969; Kahneman, 1979; Bell, 1995; Lakshminarayanan *et al.*, 2011).

A search for components of DM in real-world lead to identification of neural correlates of value and risk in human and non-human primates (d'Acremont *et al.*, 2009; Schultz, 2010; Lakshminarayanan *et al.*, 2011; Leathers *et al.*, 2012). Human DM process takes account of the risk in addition to the mean rewards that the decisions fetch. Furthermore, many neurobiological correlates of risk sensitivity are found in support of risk-based DM in humans (Wu *et al.*, 2009; Schultz, 2010; Zhang *et al.*, 2010; Wolpert *et al.*, 2012).

An important instance of risk-based DM model is the utility function, which is a combination of value and risk information (d'Acremont *et al.*, 2009). The utility function used in the current model of PG performance derives from (Bell, 1995; d'Acremont *et al.*, 2009) study that uses the concept of utility (U) as a weighted sum of value (V), which represents expected reward, and risk (h), which denotes variance in the reward. The weighting factor, λ , involved in the linear sum of V and h , denotes risk preference (eqn. (6.17)).

$$U = V - \lambda\sqrt{h} \tag{6.17}$$

We now introduce a few terms from RL used in our study:

- State – defines the features corresponding to agent and environment.
- Policy – defines the behavior of the agent for a given time.
- Value – defines the expectation of rewards for a given state.
- Reward – defines the outcome on executing an action from a state using a policy

A policy (π) is associated with an expected value (V) of the state (s) at trial (t) (eqn.(6.18)).

$$V(t) = E_{\pi}(r(t+1) + \gamma r(t+2) + \gamma^2 r(t+3) + \dots | s(t) = s) \quad (6.18)$$

where, E is expectation and γ is the discount factor denoting the myopicity in the prediction of future rewards, and the reward is denoted by 'r'. The V update is by eqn.(6.19).

$$V(t+1) = V(t) + \eta_V \delta(t) \quad (6.19)$$

where η_V is the learning rate for V and ' δ ' is the temporal difference error or the reward prediction error, and is given by eqn. (6.20)

$$\delta(t) = r(t+1) + \gamma V(t+1) - V(t) \quad (6.20)$$

Similarly, the risk prediction error, ' $\xi(t)$ ' is denoted by eqn. (6.21).

$$\xi(t) = \delta(t)^2 - h(t) \quad (6.21)$$

where, the risk function denoted by (h) is the variance in the prediction error (eqn. (6.22))

$$h(t+1) = h(t) + \eta_{risk} \zeta(t) \quad (6.22)$$

Here η_{risk} is the learning rate for risk. We now introduce a modified version of Utility (U) (eqn. (6.17)), as follows,

$$U(t) = V(t) - \alpha \text{sign}(V(t)) \sqrt{h(t)} \quad (6.23)$$

where ' $\alpha \text{sign}(V(t))$ ' is the risk preference (Pragathi Priyadharsini *et al.*, 2012).

The sign (V) term achieves a familiar feature of human decision making viz., risk-aversion for gains and risk-seeking for losses (Kahneman, 1979). In other words, when V is positive (negative), U is maximized by minimizing (maximizing) risk. We now use the above basic framework for modeling the Utility as a function of F_{Gref} .

6.2.7 Computing U (F_{Gref}) :

We now explain how the above-described Utility function formulation is applied in the present study. The Utility function, U, and its components V and h, are expressed as functions of F_{Gref} , which is taken as the state variable. A given value of F_{Gref} results in either slip or successful lift of an object. The measure of performance is expressed by CE (eqn.(6.16)).

Table 7: Parameters used in simulation; Mass of the object (M_o), friction coefficient (μ) and noise added (v) for different cases simulated in the study. Published in (Gupta *et al.*, 2013).

	Ingvarsson et al 1997 silk surface	Ingvarsson et al 1997 sandpaper surface	Fellows et al 1998
M_o (in kg)	0.3	0.3	0.33
μ	0.44	0.94	0.44
v	Uniformly Distributed $\in [-3,3]$ N	Uniformly Distributed $\in [-1.5,1.5]$ N	Uniformly Distributed $\in [-3,3]$ N
Conditions Simulated	Controls, PD OFF, PD ON	Controls, PD OFF, PD ON	Controls, PD ON

The value 'V' and risk 'h' are computed as a function of F_{Gref} by repeatedly simulating lift for a range of values around F_{Gref} . This helps us to analyze the possible variability caused on the performance of the PG task with F_{Gref} . A range of values were obtained by adding uniformly distributed noise (v : refer Table 7) to F_{Gref} (eqn.(6.25)). We modeled v to proportionally represent the F_{crit} i.e. the value of v is increased for a low μ .

The relation between noise v and friction coefficient μ is given in eqn(6.24)

$$v = 3(1.44 - \mu) \quad (6.24)$$

$$F_{Gref} = F_{Gref} + v \quad (6.25)$$

For the given value of \hat{F}_{Gref} , V_{CE} was drawn from the performance measure (eqn.(6.16)) and is generated using the cost function CE as (eqn. (6.26)). Refer Fig. 6.4 for the block diagram for determining V_{CE} .

$$V_{CE} \left(\hat{F}_{Gref} \right) = e^{-CE(\hat{F}_{Gref})} \quad (6.26)$$

Fig. 6.4: Block diagram showing the generation of error function (V_{CE}) for the input F_{Gref} . Published in (Gupta *et al.*, 2013)

There is no explicit reward in the present formulation. V_{CE} represents a reward-like quantity, the average of which is linked to value. Value (eqn.(6.27)) and risk (eqn.(6.28)) were calculated as the mean and variance of the V_{CE} ,

$$V(F_{Gref}) = mean \left(V_{CE} \left(\hat{F}_{Gref} \right) \right) \quad (6.27)$$

$$h(F_{Gref}) = var \left(V_{CE} \left(\hat{F}_{Gref} \right) \right) \quad (6.28)$$

We now have a set of numerical values of F_{Gref} and the corresponding V and h values. These numerical values are used to model V and h as explicit functions of F_{Gref} using Radial Basis Function Neural Networks (RBFNNs) explained in following subsection. The above mentioned eqns. (6.27)-(6.28) is general to all the trials.

6.2.8 Training Radial Basis Function Neural Networks

In order to determine U in PG performance we first need to identify the state and the reward signal. Since F_{Gref} is the key variable that decides the final outcome, F_{Gref} at trial, 't', is treated as a state variable.

As described earlier, calculation of $U(F_{\text{Gref}}(t))$ requires $V(F_{\text{Gref}}(t))$ and $h(F_{\text{Gref}}(t))$ as explicit functions of $F_{\text{Gref}}(t)$. To this end we use data-modeling capabilities of neural networks to implement $V(F_{\text{Gref}})$ and $h(F_{\text{Gref}})$ as explicit functions of F_{Gref} .

Using the values of $V(F_{\text{Gref}})$ and $h(F_{\text{Gref}})$ as output and F_{Gref} as input, an RBFNN (contains 60 neurons with the centroids distributed over a range [0.1, 12] in steps of 0.2, and a standard deviation (σ_{RBF}) of 0.7) was constructed and trained to approximate $V(F_{\text{Gref}})$ and $h(F_{\text{Gref}})$. For a given $F_{\text{Gref}}(t)$, the RBFNN generates the output $\rho(F_{\text{Gref}}(t))$ given in eqn(6.29).

$$\rho(F_{Gref}(t)) = \sum_{i=1}^N w_V \varphi_m(F_{Gref}(t)) \quad (6.29)$$

where,

$$\varphi_m(F_{Gref}(t)) = \exp(-(F_{Gref}(t) - \mu_m)^2 / \sigma_m^2) \quad (6.30)$$

Here, for the m^{th} basis function, μ_m denotes the center and σ_m denotes the spread.

Using the φ that was obtained from eqn.(6.30), RBF weight for determining value, w_V , is updated in eqn.(6.31). Hence the value is the mean of all the V_{CE} 's obtained on \hat{F}_{Gref} .

$$\Delta w_V = \eta_V \Delta V_{CE}(F_{Gref}) \varphi \quad (6.31)$$

where, η_V is the learning rate maintained to be 0.1, and the change in V_{CE} is given as in eqn.(6.32).

$$\Delta V_{CE}(F_{Gref}) = e^{-CE(\hat{F}_{Gref})} - e^{-CE(F_{Gref})} \quad (6.32)$$

The risk function (h) is then the variance in the ΔV_{CE} as per eqn.(6.33). Risk is the variance seen in all the V_{CE} 's obtained on \hat{F}_{Gref} .

$$\zeta(F_{Gref}) = (\Delta V_{CE}(F_{Gref}))^2 - h(F_{Gref}) \quad (6.33)$$

The weights for risk function w_h , is updated eqn. (6.34)

$$\Delta w_h = \eta_h \zeta(F_{Gref}) \phi(F_{Gref}) \quad (6.34)$$

Here, η_h is the learning rate for risk function =0.1 and ξ is the risk prediction error (eqn.(6.33)).

From the trained RBFNN, $V(F_{Gref})$ and $h(F_{Gref})$ are calculated using eqn. (6.35) and eqn. (6.36) respectively.

$$V(F_{Gref}(t)) = w_V \quad)) \quad (6.35)$$

$$h(F_{Gref}(t)) = w_h \quad)) \quad (6.36)$$

Specifically, for a F_{Gref} chosen at trial, t , $U(F_{Gref}(t))$ is a combination of the $V(F_{Gref}(t))$ and $h(F_{Gref}(t))$. Utility, $U(F_{Gref}(t))$ (eqn. (6.37)), is then obtained in terms of V and h , as shown below:

$$U(F_{Gref}(t)) = V(F_{Gref}(t)) - \alpha \sqrt{h(F_{Gref}(t))} \quad (6.37)$$

Decisions are made by choosing actions that maximize $U(F_{Gref}(t))$. Increasing the value of α makes the decision more risk averse, while the decisions are more risk-seeking for smaller values of α . Maximizing $U(F_{Gref}(t))$ is done by a stochastic hill-climbing process called the “Go/Explore/NoGo” (GEN) method described in greater detail in earlier work (Magdoom *et al.*, 2011). We now present a brief account of the GEN method.

6.3 MODELING PG PERFORMANCE AS RISK-BASED ACTION SELECTION

The key underlying idea of the proposed model is to treat the problem of choosing the right F_G as an action selection problem and thereby suggest a link between the action selection function of the BG and PG performance. Impairment in action selection machinery of the BG under PD conditions is then invoked to explain F_G changes in PD ON and OFF conditions.

In line with the tradition of Actor-Critic approach to modeling the BG (Joel *et al.*, 2002), Chakravarthy *et al.* (2010) recently proposed a model of the BG in which value is thought to be computed in the striatum. Furthermore, it was hypothesized that the action selection function of the BG is accomplished by performing some sort of a stochastic hill-climbing over the value function computed in the striatum. This

stochastic hill-climbing method was dubbed as the “Go/Explore/NoGo” (GEN) method (Magdoom *et al.*, 2011; Kalva *et al.*, 2012), which denotes a conceptual expansion of the classical Go/NoGo picture of the BG function. As an extension of the above model, it is proposed that the striatum computes not just value but also the Utility function (Balasubramani *et al.*, 2014). Action selection is then achieved by applying the GEN method to the Utility function. In the present study, the GEN method is applied to the Utility function to estimate GF’s in control and PD conditions.

6.3.1 Neurobiological interpretation of the GEN method in controls

In chapter 2 we have already discussed the role of BG in regulating various aspects of PG task. Reiterating, in terms of classical BG functionality, the DP is known as the Go pathway since it facilitates movement and the IP is called the NoGo pathway since it inhibits movement. Striatal dopamine levels are thought to switch between Go and NoGo regimes (Albin *et al.*, 1989). Recently it was proposed that the classical Go/NoGo picture can be expanded to Go/Explore/NoGo picture, wherein a new Explore regime is inserted between the classical Go and NoGo regimes (Kalva *et al.*, 2012). This explore regime corresponds to random exploration of action space which is a necessary ingredient of any RL machinery. Kalva *et al.* (2012) show that the Explore regime arises naturally due to the chaotic dynamics of the STN-GPe loop in the IP. The three regimes together amount to a form of stochastic hill-climbing,

applied to the Value (or Utility function in the present study), known as the GEN method. The GEN method has been used in the past to describe a variety of functions of the BG, in control and PD conditions, including reaching movements (Magdoom *et al.*, 2011) and spatial navigation (Sukumar *et al.*, 2012).

Magdoom *et al.* (2011) used the GEN method to hill-climb over the value function. $\delta_V(t)$ is defined as a temporal difference in value function (eqn. (6.38)).

$$\delta_V(t) = V(F_{Gref}(t)) - V(F_{Gref}(t-1)) \quad (6.38)$$

where 't' is not 'time' but 'trial number'.

The GEN method used in Magdoom *et al.* (2011) can be summarized using the following eqn.(6.39),

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{if}(\delta_V(t) > DA_{hi}) && \Delta F_{Gref}(t) = + \Delta F_{Gref}(t-1) && \text{"Go"} && (a) \\ & \text{elseif}(\delta_V(t) > DA_{lo} \wedge \delta_V(t) \leq DA_{hi}) && \Delta F_{Gref}(t) = \psi && \text{"Explore"} && (b) \quad (6.39) \\ & \text{else}(\delta_V(t) \leq DA_{lo}) && \Delta F_{Gref}(t) = - \Delta F_{Gref}(t-1) && \text{"NoGo"} && (c) \end{aligned}$$

where, ψ is a random vector, and $\|\psi\| = \chi$, a positive constant. DA_{hi} and DA_{lo} are the thresholds at which dynamics switches between Go, NoGo and Explore regimes (eqn. (6.39)). The underlying logic of the above set of eqns. ((6.39) a-c) is as follows. If $\delta_V(t) > DA_{hi}$, the last update resulted in a sufficiently large increase in V ; therefore continue in the same direction in the next step. This case is called the “Go” (eqn.(6.39)a) regime. If $\delta_V(t) \leq DA_{lo}$, the last update resulted in a significant decrease in V ; therefore proceed in the direction opposite to the previous step. This case is called the “NoGo” (eqn.(6.39)b) regime. If $DA_{lo} < \delta_V(t) \leq DA_{hi}$, there was neither a marked increase nor decrease in V ; therefore Explore (eqn.(6.39)c) for new directions. This case is called the Explore regime. In Magdoom *et al.* (2011) we assumed a simple symmetry between DA_{hi} and DA_{lo} , such that $DA_{hi} > 0$ and $DA_{lo} = -DA_{hi}$.

However, in the present study we introduce a small variation of the above formulation of the GEN method. Instead of V , we perform hill-climbing over the Utility landscape. The three separate eqns. (eqn. (6.39)a-c) can be combined into a single eqn.(6.40) (as in Sukumar et al. (2012)), as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta F_{Gref}(t) = & A_G \log \text{sig}(\lambda_G \delta_U(t)) \Delta F_{Gref}(t-1) \\
& - A_N \log \text{sig}(\lambda_N \delta_U(t)) \Delta F_{Gref}(t-1) \\
& + A_E \psi \exp(-\delta_U^2(t) / \sigma_E^2)
\end{aligned} \tag{6.40}$$

where,

$$\delta_U(t) = U(F_{Gref}(t)) - U(F_{Gref}(t-1)) \quad (6.41)$$

and,

$$\text{logsig}(n) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-n)} \quad (6.42)$$

ΔF_{Gref} is the change in F_{Gref} and ‘t’ is the trial number; $A_{G/E/N}$ are the gains of Go/Explore/NoGo components respectively; $\lambda_{G/N}$ are the sensitivities of the Go/NoGo components respectively; ψ is a random variable uniformly distributed between -1 and 1 and σ_E is the standard deviation used for the Explore component.

Just as TD error is interpreted as dopamine signal in classical RL-based accounts of the BG function, we interpret δ_U as dopamine signal in the present study. In eqn. (6.40) above, the first term on the RHS corresponds to “Go” regime, since it is significant for large positive values of δ_U (since A_G and λ_G are positive). The second term on the RHS of eqn. (6.40) above corresponds to “NoGo” regime, since it is significant for large negative values of δ_U (due to $A_N > 0$ and $\lambda_G < 0$). The third term on

the RHS corresponds to “Explore” regime, since it is dominant for values of δ_U close to 0.

6.3.2 Neurobiological interpretation of the GEN method in PD

PD being a dopamine deficient condition, a natural way to incorporate Parkinsonian pathology is to attenuate the dopamine signal, δ_U . In Sukumar *et al.* (2012) and Magdoom *et al.* (2011), PD pathology was modeled by clamping the dopamine signal, δ_U , and preventing it from exceeding an upper threshold. The rationale behind such clamping is that with fewer dopaminergic neurons left, SNc may not be able to produce a signal intensity that exceeds a certain threshold. In the present case of PG, such a constraint is applied to δ_U . If $[a, b]$ is the natural unconstrained range of values of δ_U for controls, then for PD OFF simulation, a clamped value of δ_{Lim} changes the δ_U range to $[a, \delta_{Lim}]$ where $\delta_{Lim} < b$. Furthermore, to simulate the increase in dopamine levels in PD ON condition, due to administration of L-dopa, a positive constant is added to δ_U , thereby changing the range of δ_U in PD ON condition to $[a + \delta_{Med}, \delta_{Lim} + \delta_{Med}]$ (eqn. (6.43)).

$$\delta_U(t) = \begin{cases} [a, b] & (a) \text{ for controls} \\ [a, \delta_{Lim}] & (b) \text{ for PD OFF} \\ [a + \delta_{Med}, \delta_{Lim} + \delta_{Med}] & (c) \text{ for PD ON} \end{cases} \quad (6.43)$$

Where, $\delta_{Lim}, \delta_{Med}, a, b > 0, \delta_{Lim} < b$ and $a < b$.

6.3.3 Training the GEN parameters

The output of the GEN system is F_G from which SGF is calculated as average F_G between 4000-5000 ms of simulation time, the mean and variance of which must match with the mean and variance of SGF obtained from PG experiments under control and PD conditions (Ingvarsson *et al.*, 1997; Fellows *et al.*, 1998). The parameters to be trained are $A_{G/E/N}$ (gains of the Go/Explore/NoGo terms in eqn.(6.40)), $\lambda_{G/N}$ (sensitivity of Go/ NoGo terms in eqn.(6.40)) and σ_E (sensitivity of Explore term in eqn.(6.40)). Determination of the GEN parameters is done by optimizing a cost function CE_{GEN} given as.

$$CE_{GEN} = 2(\overline{SGF}_{expt} - \overline{SGF}_{sim})^2 + (\sigma_{expt} - \sigma_{sim})^2 \quad (6.44)$$

SGF is the stable F_G generated and σ is the variance in the error. Subscripts *expt* and *sim* denote experimental and simulated values respectively. CE_{GEN} is formulated such that more weightage is given to the SGF error and lesser to the variance in the error (eqn.(6.44)). The genetic algorithm parameters used in simulation are mentioned in Table 8.

Table 8: The Genetic Algorithm (Goldberg, 1989) option set for optimization is given in the adjoining table. Optimization toolbox 6.0, MatlabR2011a, Mathworks Inc. is used. CE_{GEN} = Cost function for optimizing GEN parameters (eqn.(6.44)); GEN=Go-Explore-NoGo (eqn.(6.40)) ; F_L : Lift force. Published in (Gupta *et al.*, 2013).

Option	Option set for determining GEN parameters
Population Size	20
Crossover fraction	0.8
Elite count	4
Generation time	1000
Function tolerance	1 e-6
Cost function	CE_{GEN}

The six model parameters ($A_{G/E/N}$, $\lambda_{G/N}$ and σ_E) of the GEN method (eqn.(6.40)) are trained to capture the following experimental conditions: Controls and PD ON conditions are obtained from Fellows *et al.* (1998), whereas controls, PD ON and OFF from Ingvarsson *et al.* (1997) for both sandpaper and silk surfaces. However, the parameters $A_{G/E/N}$, $\lambda_{G/N}$ and σ_E are not all trained separately for every experimental condition. Initial parameter values for $A_{G/E/N}$, $\lambda_{G/N}$, σ_E and α were determined (Fig. 6 (a)) by matching the SGF results for controls of Fellows *et al.* (1998); this matching is achieved by optimizing CE_{GEN} (eqn.(6.44)) using GA (Fig. 6 (a)). This initial training of GEN parameters is a kind of calibration of the parameters for a given experimental setup. Once an initial estimate of parameters was obtained, $A_{G/E/N}$, $\lambda_{G/N}$ and σ_E were fixed and optimal values of α , δ_{Lim} and δ_{Med} were obtained using GA for the PD conditions, of Fellows *et al.* (1998). Similarly, for Ingvarsson *et al.* (1997), the initial parameter values for $A_{G/E/N}$, $\lambda_{G/N}$, σ_E and α were determined by matching the SGF results for controls using eqn. (6.44). For the cases of PD ON and PD OFF

(Ingvarsson *et al.*, 1997), the search space was limited to α , δ_{Lim} , δ_{Med} , by having fixed the values of $A_{G/E/N}$, $\lambda_{G/N}$, σ_E obtained from controls.

The model was tested (Fig. 6.5 (b)) using the trained GEN parameters to determine if the model generated outputs are close to the experimental values.

Fig. 6.5: Block diagram showing (a) training of GEN parameters using CE_{GEN} ; (b) model testing using trained GEN parameters. Published in (Gupta *et al.*, 2013).

6.4 RESULTS

We now apply the model described in the previous section to explain the experimental results for two published studies (Ingvarsson *et al.*, 1997; Fellows *et al.*, 1998). For

simplicity we used only constant weight trials (i.e. only the trials where only one load was repeatedly used for lifting). The friction coefficient was calculated as load force/slip force (Forsberg *et al.*, 1995) (eqn.(6.45)).

$$\mu = M_o g / F_{slip} \quad (6.45)$$

Fellows *et al.* (1998) investigated 12 controls, 16 PD patients and four hemi-parkinsonian patients. All the PD subjects were on medication ON state. The subjects were asked to lift the object to a height of 4-8 cm. The study comprised of two loads 3.3 N and 7.3 N. Various combinations of these two loads were used to give rise to ‘light’, ‘heavy’, ‘unload’ and ‘load’ condition. In our study, we simulated only the experimental results for the ‘light’ condition (which featured lifting the 3.3N object for all the trials) with a desired object lift height of 5 cm.

Ingvarsson *et al.* (1997) investigated the role of medication in 10 controls and 10 PD subjects under two object surface (silk and sandpaper). The task required the object to be PG–lifted to a height of 5 cm above the table. The entire experiment was divided into 3 parts (a) coordination of forces, (b) adaptation to friction and (c) rapid load changes. ‘Coordination of forces’ required the object to be lifted to 5 cm height, and maintained at that position for 4-6 seconds using PG. ‘Adaptation to friction’ required the subjects to gradually reduce the F_G on the object thereby causing slip F_{slip} is

calculated. Finally, in the ‘rapid load changes’ task a plastic disk was dropped in a padded plate thereby causing abrupt changes in F_L .

In the present study, we use the F_{crit} for determining the friction coefficient which is used to match the experimentally obtained F_G values under silk and sandpaper surfaces for coordination of forces case. Ingvarsson *et al.* (1997) reported the results in median \pm Q3 quartile format. Hence for simplicity the results are assumed to be normally distributed with mean=median and Q3=mean + 0.6745 standard deviation. The entire text reports the results in terms of mean and variance.

We now describe the simulation results starting from controller training to simulation of results from Fellows *et al.* (1998) and Ingvarsson *et al.* (1997).

6.4.1 The F_G controller

In the present model the F_G controller is designed as reference tracking controller which receives F_{Gref} as the input and generates a time-varying $F_G(T)$ as the output. So in the proposed configuration the F_G controller is only affected by the input (F_{Gref}) it receives. Using the overshoot ratio, $M_p=1.25$, (eqn. (6.2)) and time to peak, $T_p=530$ ms, (eqn. (6.3)) as design criteria (M_p and T_p values obtained from Johansson *et al.* (1984)), we determined $\omega_n=6.4$ and $\zeta=0.4$ as the parameters for transfer function of the F_G controller (eqn. (6.1)) (Ogata, 2002). Fig. 6.6 (a) shows the FG profile (for T=

5000 ms) for the input $F_{Gref} = 10$ N. Since the F_G controller is modeled as a transfer function which is dependent only on the F_{Gref} value, the controller did not require retraining for different friction conditions.

Fig. 6.6: Figure shows a single trial simulated output obtained from model. (a) The typical F_G profile for the input $F_{Gref} = 10$ N. The object and finger position for (b) Ingvarsson et al 1997 silk surface ($\mu=0.44$, $M_o=0.3$ kg) ; (c) Ingvarsson et al 1997 sandpaper surface ($\mu=0.94$, $M_o=0.3$ kg) ; (d) Fellows et al 1998 ($\mu=0.44$, $M_o=0.33$ kg) are shown. Note that in generation of (b-d), the F_{Gref} is kept constant at 10N for illustration purpose. Published in (Gupta *et al.*, 2013).

6.4.2 The F_L controller

The efficacy of F_L controller output can be observed in the output object and finger position. If a suboptimal F_L is generated, the object does not reach the reference position. The cardinal components affecting the object-finger slip are μ and M_o (Refer Table 7 for the values of μ and M_o) used in simulation. Since the F_L controller is affected by μ and M_o , a decreased μ or increased M_o increases the F_{crit} . Therefore, in this study we trained the F_L controller for the minimum μ and the maximum M_o to prevent the object from slipping even when μ increases or M_o decreases. Furthermore, to train the F_G controller, we assume a sufficiently large F_G ($=10$ N) thereby effectively decoupling the F_G controller. With a large, constant F_G , the cost function (CE) (eqn.(6.16)) was optimized using the GA (Goldberg, 1989; Whitley, 1994) for the setup parameters from Fellows *et al.* (1998) ($\mu=0.44$ and $M_o=0.33$ N) to obtain PID parameter values. The PID parameter values obtained were $K_{P,L}= 6.938$, $K_{I,L}=14.484$, $K_{D,L}=1.387$, $\tau_s =0.087$. The same PID parameters were used to simulate results from Ingvarsson *et al.* (1997) also. In Fig. 6.6, the output of the simulated finger and object position is shown for (b) the silk surface of Ingvarsson *et al.* (1997), (c) the sandpaper surface of Ingvarsson *et al.* (1997) and (d) light condition of Fellows *et al.* (1998).

Since we fixed the PID parameters for the F_L controller, efficacy of the PID parameters across the three control conditions viz. Ingvarsson *et al.* (1997) silk

surface, Ingvarsson *et al.* (1997) sandpaper surface and Fellows *et al.* (1998), needs to be determined. Two important criteria for determining a successful lift are: low slip ($\bar{X}_{fin} - \bar{X}_o$) and low position error ($X_{ref} - \bar{X}_o$). In all the three cases (refer Table 7) the finger–object slip distance was <0.005 m and the $X_{ref} - \bar{X}_o < 0.001$ m, where, \bar{X}_o is average position between simulation time (T) as 4000ms and 5000ms. The F_G controller output is shown in Fig. 6.6 (a) ; object and hand position for Ingvarsson *et al.* (1997) silk, Ingvarsson *et al.* (1997) sandpaper and Fellows *et al.* (1998) is shown in Fig. 6.6 (b-d). Note that F_{Gref} is held constant at 10 N.

6.4.3 Obtaining $V(F_{Gref})$, $h(F_{Gref})$ and $U(F_{Gref})$

Utility based approach requires estimation of $V(F_{Gref})$ and $h(F_{Gref})$. V and h are generated for Ingvarsson silk and Ingvarsson sandpaper and were obtained using the parameters given in Table 7. We assumed the noise to be inversely related to the friction coefficient. Hence a higher noise was used in case of lower μ and vice versa.

Note that value functions (expressed as a function of F_{Gref} (eqn. (6.35)) in case of PG are expected to have a sigmoidal shape, since a F_G level that exceeds the F_{crit} always results in a successful grip-lift and therefore reward. On the contrary, the risk function, h (eqn.(6.36)), is expected to be bell-shaped since risk is the highest in the neighborhood of slip force, and zero far from it.

Fig. 6.7: Figure showing the output (a) (value and risk) and (b) utility ($\alpha = 0.3$ and $\alpha = 0.5$) of the RBF network as an average value of 20 runs for (i) Fellows et al 1998 (ii) Ingvarsson et al 1997 silk surface, and (iii) Ingvarsson et al 1997 sandpaper surface. Published in (Gupta *et al.*, 2013).

These observations are supported by the value and risk functions constructed for various experimental conditions—Fellows *et al.* (1998) light and Ingvarsson *et al.* (1997) silk surface and sandpaper surface. Fig. 6.7 (i) shows the value and risk functions for Fellows *et al.* (1998), Fig. 6.7 (ii) shows the value and risk functions for Ingvarsson *et al.* (1997) silk surface and Fig. 6.7 (iii) shows the the value and risk functions for Ingvarsson *et al.* (1997) sandpaper surface.

6.4.4 Performing Action selection using the BG and simulating the control and PD cases of the study

Two features mark the difference in $V(F_{Gref})$ and $h(F_{Gref})$ between controls and PD. In PD OFF case we apply the clamped $\delta_U (= \delta_{Lim})$ condition (eqn.(6.43)b), whereas in PD ON case we add a positive constant (δ_{Med}) to δ_U (eqn.(6.43)c). In addition to these changes in the dopamine signal, δ_U , we assume altered risk sensitivity in PD. Studies also suggest altered risk taking in PD patients (in particular, risk in PD ON > risk in PD OFF) when compared to healthy controls (Cools *et al.*, 2003). Since α represents risk sensitivity in the utility function (eqn.(6.37)), we use a smaller α in PD case (both ON and OFF). (Refer Table 9-Table 10 for the simulated values).

Table 9: Table showing the GEN parameters and Utility parameters for Fellows et al (1998) control and PD ON. Published in (Gupta *et al.*, 2013).

	Fellows et. al. (1998)	
	Norm	PD ON
λ_G	1.53	1.53
λ_N	-7.18	-7.18
σ_E	1.00	1.00
A_G	0.01	0.01
A_N	1.60	1.60
A_E	0.43	0.43
α	0.70	0.312
δ_{Lim}	1.00	-0.5
δ_{Med}	0.00	0.427

As described earlier, the GEN method (eqn.(6.40)) produces a series of SGF values with a certain mean and standard deviation computed over the trials. It may be recalled, that eqn. (6.40) represents a form of stochastic hill-climbing over the utility function, U . It represents a map from $F_{\text{Gref}}(t-1)$ to $F_{\text{Gref}}(t)$, where ‘t’ represents the trial number. The three terms on the RHS of eqn. (6.40) represent GO, NOGO and Explore regimes, in that order. The three regimes are active under conditions of high, low and moderate dopamine (δ_U) respectively. Fig. 6.8 shows some sample profiles of the three terms on the RHS of eqn.(6.40).

Fig. 6.8: Figure illustrating output of the GO ($\lambda_G=2$), NOGO ($\lambda_N=-2$), explore ($\sigma_E=1$) regime and the overall output of the three regimes. Here $A_G=A_N=A_E=1$. The $\Delta F_{\text{Gref}}(t-1)$ is set to 1. We thereby analyse the selection output $\Delta F_{\text{Gref}}(t)$ as a function of δ_U alone. The ‘overall’ graph is produced by actually adding the noise term (III term on RHS in eqn.(6.40)). Note the high variability in $\Delta F_{\text{Gref}}(t)$ in the vicinity of $\delta_U = 0$. Published in (Gupta *et al.*, 2013).

Table 10: Table showing the GEN parameters and Utility parameters for simulating both Ingvarsson et al (1997) silk surface and sandpaper surface in controls, PD OFF and PD ON conditions.

	Ingvarsson et. al. 1997		
	Norm	PD OFF	PD ON
λ_G	1.53	1.53	1.53
λ_N	-7.18	-7.18	-7.18
σ_E	1.00	1.00	1.00
A_G	0.60	0.60	0.60
A_N	2.16	2.16	2.16
A_E	0.29	0.29	0.29
α	0.50	0.30	0.30
δ_{Lim}	1.00	0.5	0.5
δ_{Med}	0.00	0.00	0.005

Using the GEN policy on δ_U , we simulate our model with parameters described in Table 9-Table 10. However a simulation with δ_V of eqn. (6.38) with the same parameter set yields Fig. 6.9. In none of the conditions with either high noise (± 0.5 N) or low noise (± 0.25 N) Fellows *et al.* (1998) results could be reproduced.

Fig. 6.9: Comparison of GF generated under different cell loss conditions (0% resembling controls and 25% and 50% represent 25% and 50% clamping of δ in PD patients). The experimentally recorded values were 4.33N (for 0% clamping) and 7.72 N (for assumed loss of 25% or 50% clamping) Fellows et al (1998). In none of the cases (25% or 50% clamping) the required results could be reproduced. Published in (Gupta *et al.*, 2013)

6.4.5 Procedure to Train the GEN parameters

- The change in F_{Gref} (i.e. ΔF_{Gref}) from trial, 't' to 't+1' is given in eqn. (6.40).
- This eqn. (6.40) contains six parameters ($A_{G/E/N}$, $\lambda_{G/N}$ and σ_E) whose values need to be determined.
- The training for GEN parameters ($A_{G/E/N}$, $\lambda_{G/N}$ and σ_E) was carried out using GA for optimizing CE_{GEN} on Fellows *et al.* (1998) control condition experimental data. (Fig. 6.5 (a))
- The GEN parameters obtained from the control conditions are also used for simulating PD. In case of Fellows *et al.* (1998), the parameters from controls are used for PD ON only. In case of Ingvarsson *et al.* (1997), the parameters from controls are used in PD ON and OFF for two surfaces– silk and sandpaper.
- In PD OFF case, only δ_{Lim} and α are trained. In PD ON case, δ_{Lim} , δ_{Med} and α are trained.

6.4.6 Simulation of Fellows *et al.* (1998) results

Fellows *et al.* (1998) for controls was simulated using the parameters (Table 10) obtained by optimizing GA on CE_{GEN} .

- Using the $A_{G/E/N}$, $\lambda_{G/N}$, σ_E and $\alpha = 0.7$ obtained from the GA, the controls was simulated using $\delta_{Lim} = 1$ and $\delta_{Med} = 0$.
- A similar approach was performed for modeling the PD ON condition. The parameters ($A_{G/E/N}$, $\lambda_{G/N}$ and σ_E) were the same as the controls, while the values of $\alpha = 0.312$, $\delta_{Lim} = -0.5$ and $\delta_{Med} = 0.427$ were obtained by GA optimization. For a detailed list of parameters see Table 9.

A comparison of the experimental and simulated data obtained for Fellows *et al.* (1998) using the parameters in Table 9 is given as Fig. 6.10.

Fig. 6.10: Comparison of experimental (Fellows *et al.* 1998) and simulation results for SGF. The bars represent mean (\pm SEM). The results for the control and PD

ON groups are statistically significant with the p-value < 0.05 in both the experiment and simulation. Published in (Gupta *et al.*, 2013).

6.4.7 Simulation of Ingvarsson *et al.* (1997) results

Following the simulation of the Fellows *et al.* (1998) experiment:

- The results of the Ingvarsson *et al.* (1997) controls for both sandpaper surface and silk surface were simulated for obtaining ($A_{G/E/N}$, $\lambda_{G/N}$, σ_E , and $\alpha = 0.5$) using GA (Table 10). The other parameters are set as $\delta_{Lim} = 1$ and $\delta_{Med} = 0$.
- In PD ON condition, the same control parameters ($A_{G/E/N}$, $\lambda_{G/N}$ and σ_E) were used along with $\alpha = 0.30$, $\delta_{Lim} = 0.5$ and $\delta_{Med} = 0.005$ obtained through GA optimization.
- PD OFF condition was shown by optimizing $\alpha = 0.30$, $\delta_{Lim} = 0.5$ and $\delta_{Med} = 0$ with the parameters ($A_{G/E/N}$, $\lambda_{G/N}$ and σ_E) remaining the same as that of the controls.

Fig. 6.11: Comparison of experimental (Ingvarsson *et al.* 1997) and simulation results for SGF for silk surface. The bars represent the median ($\pm Q3$ quartile). The results for the control and PD ON groups are statistically significant with the p-value < 0.05 . Published in (Gupta *et al.*, 2013).

A comparison of the experimental and simulated data obtained for Ingvarsson *et al.* (1997) for silk and sandpaper using the parameters in Table 10 is given as Fig. 6.11 and Fig. 6.12, respectively. In order to be consistent with the experimental result the simulation results in Fig. 6.11-Fig. 6.12 are shown in median $\pm Q3$. Fig. 6.10-Fig. 6.12 replicate the empirical findings (both mean / median and variance profiles) well. Fellows *et al.* (1998) results show that the mean (SGF) is higher in PD ON case compared to controls ($SGF_{norm} < SGF_{PDON}$) (Fig. 6.10). A similar result ($SGF_{norm} < SGF_{PDON}$) is also reported in Ingvarsson *et al.* (1997) silk (Fig. 6.11) and sandpaper surface (Fig. 6.12). Furthermore, var (SGF) under PD OFF cases is observed to be greater than that of controls. It may be inferred that the increase in

SGF during the PD conditions would be due to their increased SM while playing risk aversive in the game of risk based decision making. This increased SM could be needed to oppose the increased internal perturbations / sensory-motor incoordination observed in the PD patients.

Fig. 6.12: Comparison of experimental (Ingvarsson *et al.* 1997) and simulation results for SGF for sandpaper surface. The bars represent the median (\pm Q3 quartile). The results for the comparison on controls-PD ON, controls-PD OFF and PD ON-PD OFF in both the experiment and simulation are non-significant in both the experiment and simulation. Published in (Gupta *et al.*, 2013).

6.5 DISCUSSION

In this paper, we present a computational model to explain the changes in F_G in control and PD ON/OFF conditions (Ingvarsson *et al.*, 1997; Fellows *et al.*, 1998). To

our knowledge this is the first computational model of PG performance in PD conditions. A novel aspect of the proposed approach to modeling PG is to apply (based on the observation that PG performance involves a SM) concepts from risk-based DM to explain F_G generation. To this end, we applied a recent model of the BG action selection based on the utility function formulation, instead of value function, to explain PG performance (Pragathi Priyadharsini *et al.*, 2012).

There are significant challenges involved in developing a computational model of PG in PD conditions. The root cause of this difficulty is that the pathology in PD is located at a high level (dopaminergic neurons of the BG) in motor hierarchy, while the motor expression is at the lowest level in the hierarchy (finger forces). Ideally speaking, a faithful computational model must incorporate these two well-separated levels in motor hierarchy, and all the levels in between. But development of such an extensive model would be practically infeasible, and may not be essential to the problem at hand. On the other hand, if model compactness is the sole governing principle, one may build an empirical, data-fitting model that links experimental parameters like friction, object weight, and abstract neural parameters like dopamine level, medication level, with observed data like mean and variance of FG generated. But such an over-simplified model could be a futile mathematical exercise without much neurobiological content.

Therefore a conservative approach to model PG performance in PD would have two components: 1) a minimal model of sensory-motor loop dynamics involved in generating PG forces, and 2) a minimal model of the BG that incorporates the effect of dopamine changes on the BG dynamics. Whereas the BG level generates evaluations of actions (F_G) based on the rewards (successful grip performance) obtained from PG performance, the sensory-motor loop dynamics receives the command from the BG level and generates F_G . While the first component represents DM, the second represents execution. These two components must then be integrated. PD-related reduction in dopamine level in the integrated model must then be manifested as appropriate changes seen in PG forces. This is the approach adopted in the present study. Fig. 6.13 presents the grand plan of the entire model, and the training/design steps followed to build various components.

Fig. 6.13: An illustration of the entire model, the training/design steps followed to build various components and to reproduce the results of Fellows (1998) and Ingvarsson et al (1997). Published in (Gupta *et al.*, 2013).

6.5.1 Modeling the Sensorimotor Loop

The sensori-motor loop component consists of two controllers, for generating the F_G and F_L respectively, and a plant model. F_G and F_L and given as inputs to the plant model which simulates the dynamics of the object and the fingers. The error between actual and desired object positions is fed back to the F_L controller. The F_G controller receives F_{Gref} as input and generates the $F_G(T)$ profile. F_{Gref} is generated by the second component, the BG component, by a DM process. The BG component is built on the lines of Actor-Critic models of the BG, where the utility function used instead of

value function, and the dopamine signal, δ , is the temporal difference of utility (eqn.(6.41)).

6.5.2 The F_L controller forms a loop with the plant

The controller gives F_L as input to the plant and receives position error as feedback. The controller is trained by GA. The F_G controller is designed as an open-loop second order system that gives F_G as input to the plant. Plant dynamics is described in chapter 4. The controller and plant system, with its trained parameters, is then integrated with appropriately trained the BG models to simulate control and PD results (Ingvarsson *et al.*, 1997; Fellows *et al.*, 1998).

6.5.3 Fellows *et al.* (1998)

Incorporating the values of object mass ($M_o=0.33$ kg) and friction ($\mu =0.44$) from Fellows *et al.* (1998), the controller and plant system trained above is used to calculate V and h functions. The V and h functions thus computed are explicitly modeled using RBFNNs. The V and h functions are combined to produce the utility function, which is used in the GEN method to produce mean (SGF) and var (SGF) as outputs. The parameters of the GEN method must be calibrated to each experimental setup. Thus the GEN parameters ($A_{G/E/N}$, $\lambda_{G/N}$ and σ_E) are trained by GA to produce the mean (SGF) and var (SGF) corresponding to the controls case. Then for the PD

ON case, only δ_{Lim} and δ_{Med} are optimized ($A_{G/E/N}$, $\lambda_{G/N}$ and σ_E are unchanged). Simulated and experimental values of mean (SGF) and var (SGF) approximate the experimental mean (SGF) and var (SGF) (see Fig. 6.11 and Fig. 6.12).

6.5.4 Ingvarsson *et al.* (1997)

The case of *Ingvarsson et al. (1997)* is a bit more complicated since it involves two friction conditions: silk and sandpaper. It also involves both PD ON and OFF unlike *Fellows et al. (1998)* which describes results for only PD ON. For the condition of sandpaper, object mass ($M_o = 0.3$ kg) and friction ($\mu = 0.94$) are incorporated into the trained controller and plant system. V and h functions are computed and explicitly modeled using RBFNNs and Utility function is computed by combining V and h. The Utility function is used in the GEN method; the GEN parameters ($A_{G/E/N}$, $\lambda_{G/N}$ and σ_E) are trained to minimize CE_{GEN} (eqn. (6.44)) so as to calibrate the model for the sandpaper surface of *Ingvarsson et al. (1997)*. The trained GEN parameters are used for the PD OFF case and only δ_{Lim} is trained to optimize CE_{GEN} . The same GEN parameters are again used for the PD ON case, where both δ_{Lim} and δ_{Med} are optimized. A similar procedure is followed for the ‘silk’ case ($M_o = 0.3$ kg and $\mu = 0.44$) of *Ingvarsson et al. (1997)* as outlined in Fig. 6.13.

Risk-based decision making can arise in both motor and cognitive domains (*Claassen et al., 2011*). The present study deals with risk in motor domain. In this context, an

interesting question naturally arises. Is there a correlation between risk-sensitivity in motor and cognitive domains. Does impaired risk-sensitivity in one domain carry over to the other? In other words, do PD patients show impaired decision making in motor and cognitive domains equally? In order to answer the above line of questioning, we propose to use a task, the Balloon Analog Risk Task (BART), which tests risk-sensitivity in cognitive domain (Claassen *et al.*, 2011). We then propose to adapt that BART to the motor domain.

In BART, the subject is asked to press a key and inflate a virtual balloon displayed on the monitor. For every key press, the virtual balloon is inflated by a fixed amount and the subject earns a fixed number of points. The catch lies in that, on inflation beyond a threshold volume, the balloon bursts and the subject loses all the points. Knowing when to stop and redeem all the points earned so far involves risk based decision making.

The above task, which is a cognitive task, can be redesigned in terms of motor function, specifically in terms of PG performance. Just as in the BART task there is a threshold point at which the balloon bursts, in PG task there is a threshold F_G at which the object slips. In the redesigned BART task, the subject will earn more points as he/she grips the object with the F_G as close as possible to the slip force. Uncertainty can be incorporated by using objects that look identical but with different weights. It will be interesting to see possible parallels in performance of normal or PD patients,

on both the cognitive and PG versions of the BART. If the above line of experimentation confirms that there is correlation between risk-sensitivity in motor and cognitive domains, it would place risk-based decision making approach to understanding PD on a stronger foundation.

CHAPTER 7

DISCUSSION

The aim of this thesis is to develop a computational model for precision grip performance in healthy controls and PD patients. Even when physical properties like size, weight, surface curvature and object surface are fixed, the grip force developed is dependent on friction between the finger and the object. Grip forces generated are higher for lesser skin friction. Therefore, the effect of skin friction which is individual dependent, must also be factored in, in order to accurately interpret the grip force changes in PD subjects. An alternative approach would be to artificially alter the skin-object surface by inserting a material with known friction. This latter approach was followed in the PG studies of (Fellows *et al.*, 1998) and (Ingvarsson *et al.*, 1997) with PD patients.

Although our PG model of chapter 6, which compares grip forces under normal and PD conditions uses a predetermined friction value, in accordance with the experimental studies (Ingvarsson *et al.*, 1997; Fellows *et al.*, 1998) that it seeks to model, we found the study of the role of skin friction on PG performance of intrinsic interest. Therefore, the first model of PG introduced in chapter 4, was used to study changes in grip force under conditions of variable friction. Two forms of friction variation were considered: 1) intrinsic friction (high and low), and 2) acutely altered

friction (dry and wet). The PGF was found to be significantly different between ‘high’ and ‘low’ friction populations, whereas the SGF was significantly different between ‘dry’ and ‘wet’ conditions. These changes were also reflected in the computational model (see chapter 5).

The PG model of chapter 4 consists of two controllers - one for generating grip force and the other for lift force. Both the controllers received feedback from the object – the lift force controller receives position-related feedback, while the grip force controller receives slip feedback. The above model cannot be used, in its current form, as a model of PG in PD conditions, since there is no specific association of model components with BG. To develop such a model, the following considerations need to be addressed.

PG performance, like any other aspect of motor function, is subserved by an elaborate hierarchy of neural substrates in the motor system, where the BG is only one, albeit crucial, component (Fig. 7.1). But since the current focus is on PG performance in PD subjects, the BG must be given special attention in the model. Furthermore, since PD is a dopamine deficient condition, minimally speaking, dopamine must be represented by a variable, which can be appropriately varied to simulate PD conditions. In a conservative modeling approach, it is reasonable to assume that changes in BG are the sole changes that distinguish a PD subject from a healthy control. Therefore, the proposed model of PG can be envisioned to have a component that corresponds to

BG, and another that translates the changes in BG into actual PG-related motor performance.

Fig. 7.1: An overview of the motor system involved in force generation.

Computational studies with a network model of BG by Chakravarthy and colleagues (Chakravarthy *et al.*; Kalva *et al.*, 2012) suggested that the classical Go-NoGo picture of BG function needs to be expanded by inserting an Explore regime between Go and NoGo. It was also shown that the resulting model can be reduced to a lumped model – dubbed the Go-Explore-NoGo (GEN) model—whose learning dynamics are described

using concepts from Reinforcement Learning. The GEN model has been applied to model a range of functions including reaching (Magdoom *et al.*, 2011), spatial navigation (Sukumar *et al.*, 2012), gait (Muralidharan *et al.*, 2014) and voluntary movements (Chakravarthy, 2013) in both normal and PD conditions.

The GEN model is also used to model BG in the proposed model of PG performance under PD conditions. However, the GEN model is used here in an altered form, different from that of (Magdoom *et al.*, 2011; Sukumar *et al.*, 2012; Chakravarthy, 2013; Muralidharan *et al.*, 2014) since risk-based decision making is incorporated in the present model on the lines of the model described in (Balasubramani *et al.*, 2014). In addition to the modified GEN model for BG, the proposed model of PG has a component that represents the sensory-motor loop dynamics. This sensory motor loop component is a modified form of the PG model described in chapter 4.

In this model, the grip force controller was modified to a second order controller. The controller receives a reference grip force (F_{Gref}) as the input and generates a grip force profile as an output. Depending on the F_{Gref} , the lift will either end up in success or a failure. We exploited this feature of the model, and incorporated it to determine F_{Gref} for healthy controls and PD patients ON and OFF medication. $F_{\text{Gref}} \pm \text{noise}$ was used to obtain mean (value) and variance (risk). The mean and variance was used to train an RBF to obtain corresponding to the input F_{Gref} . Following which utility was computed for the F_{Gref} . The GEN algorithm was then used to maximize utility. The

change in utility (contrary to value as demonstrated by Gurney *et al.* (2001a), Gurney *et al.* (2001b) and Prescott (2007)) was thought to be represented by dopamine signal. Dopamine modulated the activity of the GO, Explore and NoGo pathway. Simulation studies suggested that the development of safety margin by the PD patients can be explained by this model. Since, PD is a dopamine deficient condition, it was natural to limit the dopamine in PD OFF case and add a small additional DA to this limited value for PD ON case. We obtained simulation results very closely matching the experimental results. To our knowledge this is the first model of precision grip in PD patients.

The proposed model provides a framework on the basis of which various motor tasks involving safety margin can be modeled for controls and PD patients. It seems possible that the model might be able to predict the dopamine levels available in brain during the period of experimentation, by measuring the grip force the patients generate. Once the model is presented with a large data, it might be able to draw inferences regarding age, friction coefficient and dopamine together affecting the PGP. This may enable us to make meaningful conclusions about the dopamine in brain and the grip force a subject generates. This may help in designing patient specific medication regime.

The current model requires a large precision grip data set (for both controls and PD patients) with subjects belonging to different ages (>50 years) and with different skin

friction coefficient. A limitation of this model is that even though the model can estimate the dopamine concentration available in striatum during the experimental task, but the absence of dopamine biochemical/electrophysiological data from the brain makes it difficult to verify simulated results. Obtaining the activity of the dopaminergic cell firing in PG task in both controls and PD patients may open new avenues to further understand and elaborate the involvement of dopamine in such tasks. A further addition to the model can be inclusion of the sensory impairment due to denervation in PD patients.

Fig. 7.2 A simplified view of the risk based decision making model for the precision grip task.

One other salient feature in the Utility equation (eqn.(6.23)) is the risk sensitivity term (α). Prior studies suggest that the neuromodulator serotonin could also be an underlying factor in the exhibition of differential risk sensitivity in PD patients (Fahn *et al.*, 1971; Balasubramani *et al.*, 2014). Reduced levels of serotonin repress the behavioral inhibition. In a precision grip task, reduced levels of serotonin weakens the termination signal for action selection, thus the PD patients show an increase in PG compared to controls. Most of the precision grip experiments in PD revolve solely around the dopamine hypothesis. In the current study (similar to Balasubramani *et al.* (2014)), we determined a significant role of serotonin in PD motor performance. Therefore, experimental studies must be conducted to support the role of serotonin together with dopamine affecting the precision grip performance of both the controls and PD patients.

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LIST OF PAPERS BASED ON THESIS

- **Gupta, A.,** P. P. Balasubramani and V. S. Chakravarthy (2013). Computational model of precision grip in Parkinson's disease: a utility based approach. *Front Comput Neurosci*, **7**: 172. ([DOI: 10.3389/fncom.2013.00172](https://doi.org/10.3389/fncom.2013.00172))
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